

D5.5: Validation and Evaluation Report (first version)

PROJECT	
Project Number	101120962
Project Acronym	RESCALE
Project Title	Revolutionised Enhanced Supply Chain Automation with Limited Threats Exposure
Start Date	01.10.2023
Programme	HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-02
DELIVERABLE	
Deliverable Type	Report
Workpackage	WP5
Deliverable Lead	UNSPMF
Editors	Danijela Boberic Krsticev (UNSPMF)
Contributors	All partners
Dissemination Level	Public

Abstract

The current document is an initial validation and evaluation report on the fulfillment of the functional and non-functional requirements identified in D2.3. As part of the validation process, each component is validated individually and within the more extensive integrated system to ensure seamless interoperability and alignment with predefined requirements. In addition, the project defined a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that serve as benchmarks to measure the project's success in achieving its research and development objectives, and this deliverable includes a report on the status of those KPIs. Furthermore, this deliverable presents an evaluation survey designed to collect user feedback during software demonstrations at info days and similar events, providing valuable insight into the software's usability, usefulness, and adoption potential among stakeholders. Through this deliverable, RESCALE establishes a structured and dynamic framework for continuous validation and evaluation, reinforcing the reliability, security, and overall effectiveness of its solutions while aligning with project goals and industry standards.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101120962

Internal Reviewers

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Revisions

Version	Date	Partner	Overview
0.1	10/01/2025	UNSPMF	ToC
0.2	14/03/2025	All partners	First round of input
0.3	23/03/2025	All partners	Second round of input
0.4	25/03/2025	UNSPMF	Aligning terminology and formatting across sections
0.5	31/03/2025	PST, CC, AEGIS, ISI	Internal review started
0.6	10/04/2025	All partners	Review comments addressed
1.0	11/04/2025	UNSPMF	Final version

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List of Abbreviations

- API** Application Programming Interface. 17
- BOV** Bill of Vulnerabilities. 64
- CD** Continuous Deployment. 19, 27
- CI** Continuous Integration. 19, 27
- CLI** Command-Line Interface. 20, 27
- CPA** Correlation Power Analysis. 44
- CPE** Common Platform Enumeration. 82
- CVE** Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures. 18, 26, 27, 32, 39, 53, 56
- CWE** Common Weakness Enumeration. 22, 23, 26, 27, 39, 52
- DL** Deep Learning. 17, 22–24, 32
- DSCG** Dynamic Supply Chain component Guarantee. 5, 14, 15, 35, 36, 39, 44, 45, 50, 56, 65, 70, 72, 94, 104, 105
- DuT** Device Under Test. 45, 46
- FN** False Negative. 30, 31
- FP** False Positive. 30, 31
- FPGA** Field Programmable Gate Array. 46
- IAM** Identity and Access Management. 14, 105
- iKPI** Impact Key Performance Indicator. 101
- JSON** JavaScript Object Notation. 22, 27, 36, 38, 40, 45, 46, 48, 51, 83, 88, 92, 97
- KPI** Key Performance Indicator. 1, 3, 7, 10, 15, 17, 28–32, 52, 53, 55, 56, 69, 71, 80, 81, 83, 84, 90, 101, 109
- LLM** Large Language Model. 24
- ML** Machine Learning. 17, 25, 26, 28, 30, 44, 45, 49
- MVP** Minimum Viable Product. 10, 17, 99, 109
- NVD** National Vulnerability Database. 15
- SARIF** Static Analysis Results Interchange Format. 21–28

SBOM Software Bill of Materials. 5, 17, 56, 65, 70, 72, 104, 105

SSCG Static Supply Chain component Guarantee. 5, 14, 15, 19–21, 25–27, 35, 36, 56, 65, 70, 72, 92, 95, 97, 104, 105

SSL Secure Sockets Layer. 61

TBOM Trusted Bill of Materials. 3, 5, 6, 10, 14, 15, 44, 56, 57, 62–65, 67–73, 78–82, 84, 103–105, 107

TDC Time-to-Digital Converter. 46

TN True Negative. 30, 31

TP True Positive. 30, 31

TRL Technology readiness levels. 11

TVLA Test Vector Leakage Assessment. 44

XML Extensible Markup Language. 83

1 Introduction

The RESCALE project adopts a two-cycle approach to validation and evaluation. The first cycle starts from the beginning of the project and ends at M18, while the second cycle includes the second half of the project, from M18 to M36. The first cycle focuses on the validation of Minimum Viable Product (MVP). The second cycle will culminate in a final assessment of RESCALE solution, ensuring that all refinements and improvements are systematically captured and analyzed. This document refers to the results of the first cycle of evaluation and validation conducted internally within the RESCALE project by the technical partners.

1.1 Scope & Contribution

This deliverable contributes to RESCALE's overall objectives by validating the effectiveness of the security assessment tools and methodologies across the supply chain lifecycle. The validation focuses on the accuracy of security testing mechanisms, the improvements in vulnerability detection, supply chain resilience and the effectiveness of AI-assisted security models. In addition, the evaluation also considers stakeholder trust in blockchain-assisted TBOM management, usability of the RESCALE solution for security and non-security experts, the overall acceptance of the platform in real-world pilot scenarios and the alignment with regulatory frameworks such as the NIS directive [3].

The first part of this deliverable contains the validation of individual components integrated into the RESCALE solution. Each component undergoes an independent validation process to ensure its functionality aligns with the specified functional and non-functional requirements. The validation involves:

- Verifying that each component meets its designated functional requirements.
- Assessing the component's individual performance against relevant KPIs.
- Identifying any gaps or deviations and proposing necessary improvements.

The second part of the deliverable refers to the system-level validation. The integrated system is assessed to ensure seamless interoperability and overall functional compliance. The system-level validation process includes:

- Evaluating the interactions between integrated components.
- Confirming that system-wide functional requirements are met.
- Measuring overall system performance against established KPIs.
- Addressing any discrepancies and defining mitigation strategies.

Where available, validation results are presented with supporting evidence. In cases where they are not yet available due to ongoing system development, verification methods are described, detailing the methodologies and tools which will be used for validation. These serve as a

foundation for future evaluations and ensure that the system progresses toward achieving its intended objectives.

In addition to the validation of individual components and the integrated system, this deliverable also presents an evaluation survey designed to gather stakeholder feedback. This survey will be conducted during the presentation of the RESACLE solution at info days and similar events. The primary objective of the survey is to assess user perceptions regarding the software's functionality, usability, adaptability and overall value. Stakeholders will provide insights on the system's ease of use, its benefits for their needs, and their likelihood of adopting it within their organizations. The feedback obtained will help refine the system and ensure it meets user expectations and industry requirements.

1.2 Relation to Work Packages, Deliverables, and Activities

This deliverable is a part of *Work Package 5 (WP5) - Integration, Deployment, and Validation*. Particularly, it presents work done in Task 5.3. In Task T5.2, the RESCALE solution and its components were deployed in a pilot environment, and initial testing was conducted. The results from those tests serve as the input for the validation and evaluation performed in Task 5.3 and presented in this deliverable. That feedback allowed us to assess the system's performance, reliability, and operability, forming the foundation for the subsequent steps for the project.

Furthermore, this deliverable is closely related to activities in Work Package 2 (WP2), where the overall high-level architecture of the RESCALE solution and initial list of functional and non-functional requirements are defined (Task 2.2). After the validation and evaluation, the insights gained will help enhance and refine that list of requirements, ensuring that the RESCALE solution evolves to meet the project's objectives more effectively. The feedback loop from the evaluation process to Task T2.2 ensures that the platform continually adapts to the identified needs and use cases.

Finally, a key element of this deliverable is gathering feedback from various stakeholders using the survey, which provides valuable insights into the effectiveness and impact of the RESCALE platform. This feedback is directly connected with the objectives of Work Package 6 (WP6), which focuses on raising awareness about supply chain security threats and maximizing the visibility of the solutions developed within RESCALE. Also, results obtained through Task 5.3 will define a solid road map for the evolution of the developed technologies to higher TRL levels, which is another objective of WP6.

1.3 Contribution to WP5 and Project Objectives

WP5 focuses on the integration, deployment, testing, demonstration, and validation of the RESCALE solution to ensure its effectiveness in real-world scenarios. This deliverable D5.5 directly contributes to the WP5 *Objective 5.4 - Validate implemented solutions against requirements and evaluate results against ambitions and targets* by providing evidence that the integrated solution is effective and functional. It provides a framework for comprehensively evaluating and validating RESCALE software and its components in the two complementary pilot use cases.

In addition, this deliverable supports general project objectives. Namely, it is in line with project's *Objective 1*, *Objective 2*, *Objective 3* (see table 1) as it provides a structured evaluation of the RESCALE software solution and its components, assessing its capability to serve as a comprehensive toolbox for auditing and enhancing supply chain security. By validating the effectiveness of the implemented security mechanisms for both hardware and software components, this deliverable ensures that the developed tools address security challenges in the supply chain. Furthermore, the validation process actively involves key stakeholders, whose engagement is essential in demonstrating the platform's real-world applicability, which is aligned with project *Objective 4*.

Project's Objective	Description
Objective 1	Design and develop a complete toolbox to audit and increase the security of the supply chain based on emerging technologies for both hardware and software modules.
Objective 2	Detect and safeguard the hardware elements of supply chain systems detecting vulnerabilities against implementation attack at the pure IP Core level and the processors level (like side-channel, cache, and microarchitectural attacks), and extend the security capabilities of software modules via innovative fuzzy hashing techniques, symbolic execution methods, static and dynamic analysis.
Objective 3	Provide a Trusted BOM approach that will infuse trust in the software and hardware supply chain and promote trusted updates.
Objective 4	Demonstrate and validate the effectiveness and accuracy of the proposed solutions in two complementary use cases with the active engagement of several stakeholders accomplishing at the end of the project a TRL4 for the entire platform.

Table 1: Project's objectives related to this deliverable

1.4 Document Structure

This section outlines the structure of the deliverable, which is divided into several key areas.

- **Section 2** - This section provides a comprehensive overview of the software architecture of the RESCALE project, detailing the key components, their interactions, and the underlying design principles.
- **Section 3** - This section focuses on the validation of individual software components, ensuring they meet the specified functional and non-functional requirements before integration.
- **Section 4** - This section examines the validation of the complete system, ensuring that all integrated components function correctly and efficiently within the overall RESCALE framework.
- **Section 5** - This section proposes the framework to assess the RESCALE solutions from the end user perspective, measuring the user experience and identifying potential areas for improvement to enhance accessibility and efficiency.

- **Section 6** - This section synthesizes the key findings and outlines recommendations for improving the final version of the RESCALE solution.

As outlined, Sections 2–4 focus on the validation of the system, ensuring its functionality and reliability. In contrast, Section 5 is dedicated to the evaluation aspect, though this process is still in its early stages. By following this structure, the document ensures a logical flow from architectural design to validation and stakeholders’ evaluation, providing a comprehensive analysis of the RESCALE project’s development and deployment process.

2 Software Architecture Overview

RESCALE is a software solution designed to enhance supply chain security by providing automated security auditing. It uses AI-assisted tools for static and dynamic assessment of software and hardware components. It ensures that all components in a product's supply chain have undergone thorough security testing, generating immutable security guarantees that are recorded on a blockchain.

The RESCALE solution can be used by three distinct user roles: Producer, Consumer and End User. The Producer is primarily a developer role who may develop a product that may be the starting point in a supply chain, such as a library or a module that may be used by Consumers or End Users. The Producer is focusing on the static analysis testing. The Consumer is a primarily a tester role with the ultimate goal of generating the DSCG and the TBOM as a next step. The Consumer may or may not have access to the source code of the product under test and will perform dynamic testing in either hardware and/or software. The End User is the final user in the supply chain, who simply wants to use a product that has been verified by the RESCALE framework.

Prior to detailed validation of RESCALE and its components, this section outlines the overall system architecture. A fully detailed description of the framework was initially introduced in *Deliverable D2.5: High-Level Architecture (first version)*, submitted in M8.

RESCALE's high-level architecture is comprised of several core components, each serving a distinct role within the system. The architecture is organized into three distinct horizontal layers, as illustrated in Figure 1:

- **Assessment Domain:** This layer encompasses the two key components that deliver the core functionalities of the project — *Static Code Analysis Module* and *Dynamic Testing Module*. Their primary purpose is to generate the Static Supply Chain component Guarantee (SSCG) and the Dynamic Supply Chain component Guarantee (DSCG), respectively, providing foundational insights into the security and integrity of supply chain components.
- **Management Domain:** The management layer focuses on user interaction and operational control. It features the *Dashboard*, the primary interface for user engagement, and the *State Manager*, which coordinates platform processes and maintains system states. Additionally, the *Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR)* plays a crucial role in generating and validating the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM). *TrustOR* ensures that security assessment outputs from various tools are properly validated, consolidated, and structured before they contribute to the TBOM. *TrustOR* also handles security alerts that may require updates or re-evaluations of existing security guarantees. These alerts are generated by the *Security Assurance Module* and sent to *TrustOR* whenever new vulnerabilities are identified. This domain also integrates essential components such as Authentication/Authorization, Identity and Access Management (IAM), and communication services to ensure seamless integration and interaction across RESCALE components.
- **Security & Trust Domain:** This foundational layer supports the platform's overall security and trust mechanisms. The *Ledger Infrastructure* offers a decentralized solution for recording and verifying TBOM entries, ensuring data immutability, transparency,

and accountability. The *Ledger Infrastructure* module utilize blockchain's immutable properties and each TBOM entry is securely recorded in a tamper-evident manner. This immutability is enforced through cryptographic hashing, which links each block to the previous one, forming a chain that is nearly impossible to alter undetected. Additionally, blockchain's consensus mechanisms are vital in preserving TBOM data integrity. These mechanisms ensure that all network nodes agree on the ledger's state, validating new entries before they are added. This decentralized validation process minimizes the risk of unauthorized modifications, as altering data would require approval from the majority of the network. The *Repositories* store SSCGs, DSCGs, and TBOMs, serving as key data sources for both TBOM generation and validation. Finally, the *Security Assurance Module* continuously monitors the security posture of the platform, automatically sending the new vulnerabilities, safeguarding the platform's integrity and resilience. The *Security Assurance Module* uses the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) as its main reference for vulnerability detection. A localized mirror of the NVD provides fast and uninterrupted access to the latest vulnerability information. While NVD is its main reference, it also includes data coming from the OSS Index [20], findings from penetrating testing tools, and repositories like Github's Advisory Database[9].

The key components identified for further validation in the following sections of this report are the *Static Code Analysis Module*, *Dynamic Testing Module*, *Dashboard*, *State Manager*, *Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR)*, *Ledger Infrastructure*, and *Security Assurance Module*. The selection of those components aligns with the critical KPIs and functional requirements defined in WP2 and WP3, ensuring that the validation efforts focus on the most important aspects of the RESCALE solution.

Figure 1: RESCALE High-level Architecture

3 Component-Level Validation

Ensuring the reliability and accuracy of individual RESCALE's components is a critical step in the validation process. Before full integration testing, component-level validation focuses on assessing each module independently to verify its functionality, performance, and compliance with predefined requirements. This process helps identify potential defects early, facilitating more efficient debugging and reducing the risk of RESCALE system failures. The individual components of the RESCALE solution, as presented in Figure 1, have been validated against requirements and KPIs previously defined in D2.3. The results of this validation are detailed in the following subsections.

3.1 Static Code Analysis Module

The Static Code Analysis Module processes software projects, specifically their source code and the SBOM associated with it, to identify and assess potential security vulnerabilities and weaknesses. It employs advanced ML/DL enhanced static code analyzers, which go beyond traditional methods to detect issues more effectively. These advanced analyzers are particularly effective at identifying security vulnerabilities (e.g., injection flaws, buffer overflows), code smells, API misuse, and performance anti-patterns. The ML/DL components play a crucial role in reducing false positives, enhancing the accuracy of the analysis compared to traditional static analysis tools.

3.1.1 Technical Requirements

The Static Code Analysis Module currently consists of several tools: Execution Engine (orchestrates all tools based on a given configuration), SSCG Generator, SAVE-ME, SASTER-cli, IVEE (Intelligent Vulnerabilities Exposure Engine), DetectEr. Each of these tools were validated against the MVP to assess the extent to which the functional requirements have been fulfilled till M18. Those assessments provide insights into the module's effectiveness, accuracy, and efficiency in real-world scenarios. Table 2 provides an overview of the identified functional and non-functional requirements, including their description, the tools (inside the Static Code Analysis Module) associated with their implementation, the method used for validation, and the current status of each requirement. Initial specification of RESCALE's functional and non-functional requirements is presented in *D2.3 - Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (first version)*.

Table 2: List of Initial Functional and Non-Functional Requirements related to the Static Code Analysis Module

TRID	Title	Tool	Validation method	Status
TR003	Source code collection	Execution Engine	Demonstration	Achieved

Table 2 – continued from previous page

TRID	Title	Tool	Validation method	Status
TR004	Static code scanning	SAVE-ME, SASTER-cli, IVEE	Demonstration	In progress
TR005	False Positive/Negative analysis of static analysis report	SAVE-ME, SASTER-cli	Demonstration	In progress
TR006	Show the results of static analysis	SSCG Generator, SASTER-cli, SAVE-ME, IVEE, DetectEr	Demonstration	In progress
TR007	Generate SSCG	SSCG Generator	Demonstration	In progress
TR012	Tools/components should be able to “download and run”	Static Code Analysis Module & Execution Engine	Demonstration	In progress
TR013	Documentation Completeness	Static Code Analysis Module, SAVE-ME, SASTER-cli	Demonstration	In progress
TR014	Docker Compatibility	SSCG Generator, SAVE-ME, SASTER-cli, IVEE, DetectEr	Demonstration	In progress
TR016	Automated Tool/Component Accessibility	Static Code Analysis Module incl. all tools	Demonstration	In progress
TR017	Secure Communication Protocol Support	SSCG Generator	Demonstration	Scheduled for M20
TR018	Machine Readable Data Input/Output	SSCG Generator, SASTER-cli, IVEE, SAVE-ME, DetectEr	Demonstration	In progress
TR022	Modules-level ingesting of crucially important data sources (CVE, etc.)	SASTER-cli, SAVE-ME	Demonstration	Scheduled for M21
TR023	Security/Cryptographic Primitive Operations	Execution Engine	Demonstration	Scheduled for M22
TR024	ML/DL for Data Classification	SAVE-ME	Demonstration	In progress
TR025	Software Property Verification	DetectEr, IVEE	Demonstration	In progress
TR026	Static Code Analysis Scalability	Static Code Analysis Module incl. all tools	Demonstration	Scheduled for M22

Table 2 – continued from previous page

TRID	Title	Tool	Validation method	Status
TR027	Static Code Analysis and Formal Verification Accuracy	SASTER-cli, IVEE, SAVE-ME	Demonstration	In progress
TR028	Static Code Analyzer and Formal Verifier Integration	DetectEr, IVEE	Demonstration	Scheduled for M22
TR029	Machine Learning Integration	SASTER-cli, SAVE-ME	Demonstration	Achieved
TR030	Language Support	SAVE-ME, SASTER-cli, IVEE, DetectEr	Demonstration	Achieved for Erlang, Python, C, C++

3.1.2 Evaluation Results

The following evaluation results provide an overview of test cases and corresponding evidence demonstrating the Static Code Analysis Module’s compliance with the defined requirements. This evaluation aims to verify that each tool operates according to its intended purpose and meets the criteria outlined in the requirement and Table 2 presented in the previous section. A dedicated evaluation is carried out separately for each tool.

3.1.2.1 Execution Engine

The Execution Engine is the central coordinator of the Static Code Analysis Module. It makes the source code available to analyzers, processes configuration settings into specific analysis actions, and manages the execution of each analyzer. Based on their results, it triggers the SSCG generation and ensures the output is pushed to the RESCALE platform. Acting as the glue of the module, it ensures all components work together smoothly to deliver verified code analysis results.

TR003 Source code collection:

The Execution Engine relies on source code being injected into the Docker container of the Static Code Analysis Module. This is commonly done in an automated way in CI/CD systems. The injected source code is then forwarded to the static code analyzers of the module.

TR012 Tools/components should be able to “download and run”:

The Static Code Analysis Module can be downloaded and started as Docker container, together with a specific configuration. This configuration is then ingested into the Execution Engine which translates it to a set of actions, e.g. the execution of analysis tools on source code and the generation of the SSCG. The user only needs to provide such configuration to the Docker container to run it, there is no need to compile or build anything.

3.1.2.2 SSCG Generator

The SSCG Generator, developed in Erlang for the RESCALE project, is a CLI tool designed for generating and managing SSCGs. The SSCG Generator consumes test reports from a single static code analysis tool and processes them into a single SSCG, which is a CycloneDX document [15]. It then sends the SSCG to the RESCALE platform, given certain configuration parameters like a URL endpoint and an authentication token.

TR006 Show the results of the static analysis:

The SSCG Generator bundles all test reports from all analyzers of the static code analysis module together into a SSCG as outlined in D3.1. This functionality has already been verified by the pilot partners but is still subject to improvements as the tools are still in development (see also D5.3).

TR007 Generate SSCG:

The SSCG is generated as outlined in D3.1 and can be published to the RESCALE platform. This functionality has already been verified by pilot partners (see D5.3) but is still subject to improvements as the tools are still under development.

TR012 Tools/components should be able to “download and run”:

The SSCG Generator can be downloaded as part of the static code analysis module and, given an appropriate configuration (e.g. access token for the RESCALE platform and a correct URL pointing to it) it works out of the box. The tool can also be used on its own as it has a CLI interface with documented options. This CLI interface is documented in D3.1. As shown in D5.3 it is possible for the pilot partners to utilize the SSCG Generator as part of the static code analysis module without any problems. An example run of the SSCG Generator is illustrated in Figure 2.

TR014 Docker Compatibility:

The SSCG Generator is embedded into the static code analysis module, which is a single Docker container. The user just has to download this container to make use of all tools related to that module. The compatibility with Docker has been verified by the pilot partners as well (see D5.3).

TR016 Automated Tool/Component Accessibility:

The SSCG Generator is indirectly configured using the configuration of the static code analysis module. The user of the module does not even directly touch the SSCG Generator; it can be used without even being aware of it. This mode of operation has also been verified by the pilot partners (see D5.3).

TR017 Secure Communication Protocol Support:

The SSCG Generator sends the SSCG to the RESCALE platform. For this purpose it is required to use authentication and encryption mechanics such that RESCALE infrastructure can be verified and data in transit can't be read by a man-in-the-middle attack. A typical example of such a mechanism is TLS. It is currently under discussion how this topic is approached and a conceptual solution is expected by M21.

```
131 Status: Downloaded newer image for harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/static_analysis_module:latest
132 Validating sbom.json...
133 BOM validated successfully.
134 [Erlang] Processing Erlang source at /user_files/src/ with output at /app/out/test-reports/
135 [SAVE-ME] Running scan...
136 [SAVE-ME] Scan completed
137 [Erlang] Erlang source scans completed
138 [SSCG Generator] Generating SSCG...
139   - SBOM Path: /user_files/sbom.json
140   - Test Report Folder: /app/out/test-reports/
141   - SSCG Path: /app/out/sscg.json
142 JSON successfully stored to /app/out/sscg.json
143
144 Validating sscg.json...
145 BOM validated successfully.
146 [SSCG Generator] Publishing SSCG...
147   - SBOM Path: /user_files/sbom.json
148   - SSCG Path: /app/out/sscg.json
149 Request successfully sent.
150
151 SSCG generation/publishing process completed.
```

Figure 2: Example Execution of the SSCG Generator as Part of PST’s CI System

TR018 Machine Readable Data Input/Output:

The SSCG Generator requires the analyzer tools to provide their test reports in a certain folder. All files in this folder are then processed into an SSCG. While the Generator itself has no hard requirements on the file content format, it is expected that the analyzer tools output their data in SARIF format (which is a standard for static code analysis data, see D3.1). The test reports are encoded with base64 and inserted as a string into the SSCG, which itself is a CycloneDX document. Hence, the overall SSCG, including the actual test reports, is machine processable.

3.1.2.3 SAVE-ME

SAVE-ME is an adaptation of the CodeBERT[6] model specifically fine-tuned to detect insecure code patterns in Erlang. The model operates at the function level, making it suitable for analyzing individual Erlang functions in isolation. This is a critical capability given Erlang’s functional programming paradigm and its emphasis on concurrent processes, where functions often encapsulate isolated logic and are triggered independently. Unlike traditional monolithic codebases, Erlang applications are typically composed of many small, self-contained functions, making function-level analysis particularly effective for identifying localized vulnerabilities.

TR004 Static code scanning:

The SAVE-ME module satisfies the requirement for static code scanning by analyzing Erlang source code without execution, identifying potential security vulnerabilities and coding issues. The scanning process is fully automated and operates on a per-function basis to ensure a fine-grained analysis.

Specifically, SAVE-ME processes a given input directory containing Erlang source files. It systematically scans each file, extracts individual functions, and passes them through the model

for analysis. The model then classifies each function based on the presence of security vulnerabilities, providing a vulnerability type prediction and a corresponding confidence score.

Currently, SAVE-ME identifies vulnerabilities using the following categories:

- `BAD_ARG` – Invalid or unexpected arguments passed to a function.
- `BAD_GENERATOR` – Errors in generator expressions, such as invalid list comprehensions.
- `BAD_KEY` – Accessing non-existent keys in maps or dictionaries.
- `BAD_MAP` – Incorrect usage or construction of map data structures.
- `BAD_RECORD` – Misuse of record fields or accessing undefined fields.
- `NO_MATCHING_CASE_CLAUSE` – Missing or unhandled cases in case expressions.
- `NO_MATCHING_FUNCTION_CLAUSE` – Pattern mismatch in function clauses with no fall-back.
- `NO_MATCH_OF_RHS` – Pattern mismatch when binding the right-hand side of a match expression.

As the dataset expands, we plan to refine these classifications by mapping detected vulnerabilities to CWE categories. This will enhance the tool's ability to align with industry standards and provide more structured vulnerability insights. The ongoing dataset development will facilitate this transition, ensuring broader and more meaningful classification capabilities in future iterations.

The results are structured and written according to the SARIF format, ensuring compatibility with security workflows and automated reporting systems.

This approach satisfies the static scanning requirement by allowing SAVE-ME to operate on a function level rather than analyzing entire files simultaneously, making it modular, scalable, and adaptable. Future improvements will continue refining detection accuracy and expanding the types of vulnerabilities identified.

TR005 False Positive/Negative analysis of static analysis report:

The SAVE-ME tool enables developers to evaluate the reliability of its vulnerability assessments by providing confidence scores alongside its predictions. Since SAVE-ME is a DL model rather than a traditional rule-based static analyzer, it does not pinpoint specific problematic lines in the code. Instead, it classifies entire Erlang functions and outputs a confidence score indicating the likelihood that a particular function contains a vulnerability.

TR006 Show the results of static analysis:

The output of SAVE-ME's static analysis is structured in JSON format following the SARIF schema and passed along the pipeline to the SSCG Generator for further processing (for more details, see TR018 below). The tool can also display the raw results in text format to the user running this tool.

TR013 Documentation Completeness:

As the tool develops, its documentation is consistently revised and enhanced. Additionally, we provide straightforward and comprehensive Docker documentation. Some details can be found in Chapter 4 of the RESCALE Deliverable D3.1, and the documentation will be extended as the project progresses.

TR014 Docker Compatibility:

The SAVE-ME sub-module satisfies the requirement for Docker compatibility by being encapsulated within a Docker container. This ensures ease of deployment, portability, and integration into existing security workflows. A dockerized version of SAVE-ME can be found in the RESCALE Harbor repository [18].

SAVE-ME is both *shipped as part of the Static Code Analysis Module container* and provided as a standalone Docker container in the RESCALE Harbor.

Users can invoke SAVE-ME using a simple Docker command, providing the necessary input and output directories. The results are generated in SARIF format, ensuring compatibility with static analysis tools. Moreover, SAVE-ME is automatically triggered within the Static Code Analysis Module when an Erlang project is detected, making its integration seamless and transparent to the end user.

For more details on SAVE-ME's Docker implementation, refer to Chapter 4 of the RESCALE Deliverable D3.1.

TR018 Machine Readable Data Input/Output:

To facilitate user interaction and verification, SAVE-ME produces its results in SARIF, a standardized format that allows security reports to be reviewed systematically. Developers can examine the reported vulnerabilities, assess the associated confidence scores, and determine whether a flagged issue represents a true positive (an actual security concern) or a false positive (an issue incorrectly reported as a vulnerability).

By structuring its output in the SARIF format, SAVE-ME ensures compatibility with existing security tools and workflows. Future improvements will focus on refining confidence estimation and integrating mechanisms to incorporate user feedback, further improving the model's precision and reducing false positives.

An example of the SAVE-ME output can be found in Appendix B.

TR022 Modules-level ingesting of crucially important data sources:

Currently, SAVE-ME is working with Erlang-specific designations of vulnerabilities. As the project continues and the dataset used to train the DL model is expanded, support will be added for CWEs.

TR024 ML/DL for Data Classification:

The SAVE-ME tool satisfies the requirement for DL-based data classification by utilizing a fine-tuned deep-learning model to determine whether an Erlang function handles vulnerable or non-vulnerable data. This classification is important for enforcing proper security measures, ensuring that vulnerable data is appropriately handled and protected against potential leaks or misuse.

To achieve this, SAVE-ME processes each Erlang function individually, analyzing its structure, parameter usage, and data flow. The model, based on the fine-tuned CodeBERT [6] variant, learns contextual patterns that distinguish vulnerable data handling from general function logic. Unlike rule-based approaches that rely on fixed keyword lists, this DL-driven approach allows SAVE-ME to generalize across different coding styles and usage patterns, improving accuracy and adaptability.

To train and refine the classification model, SAVE-ME requires a labeled dataset of Erlang functions, where each function is tagged as either vulnerable or secure. This dataset is currently being constructed using InfERL [10], a static analysis tool, to analyze various Erlang projects and extract labeled examples. The initial labels undergo manual inspection and expert validation to enhance accuracy and minimize false positives.

By integrating expert-reviewed ground truth data, SAVE-ME ensures that its DL model continuously improves in precision and reliability. The classification results, along with confidence scores, are exported in SARIF format, allowing seamless integration with security analysis tools and automated workflows.

As the dataset expands and the model is further refined, SAVE-ME will enhance its ability to recognize complex data-handling scenarios in Erlang, making static code analysis more robust and adaptable to evolving security needs. While its open-source publication and potential reuse by other RESCALE tools are topics under consideration, these aspects remain subject to future discussion and agreement within the consortium.

For further details on the CodeBERT model, SAVE-ME model, and the dataset, please refer to Chapter 4 of the RESCALE Deliverable D3.1.

TR026 Static Code Analysis Scalability:

Once the DL model is fully trained, steps will be taken to ensure its smooth operation with increasing size and number of inputs.

TR027 Static Code Analysis and Formal Verification Accuracy:

High precision of vulnerability prediction will be ensured by rigorous testing in different application scenarios and through prepared benchmarks. See KPI1.2 and KPI2.1 in the Section 3.1.3.

TR029 Machine Learning Integration:

SAVE-ME leverages a pre-trained CodeBERT-based model which is fine-tuned for vulnerability classification of Erlang source code (for more details, see TR030 below).

TR030 Language Support:

The SAVE-ME tool is designed to support static code analysis for Erlang, leveraging a pre-trained CodeBERT-based model fine-tuned for vulnerability classification. While traditional static analysis tools often require hand-crafted rules for each supported language, SAVE-ME benefits from the transfer learning capabilities of large language models (LLMs).

By using the pre-trained CodeBERT model, SAVE-ME can be adapted to different programming languages through additional fine-tuning, making it a flexible and scalable approach to vulnerability detection. This method allows the tool to learn language-specific patterns and

security risks without needing entirely new rule sets, unlike conventional static analysis tools that require manual rule definitions for each language.

Although SAVE-ME is currently tailored for Erlang, its underlying approach offers a path for extending support to other languages. Fine-tuning on additional datasets can enable the model to generalize across languages like Python and C/C++, ensuring adaptability to different coding environments while maintaining the efficiency of deep learning-based static analysis.

3.1.2.4 DetectEr

DetectEr is a runtime verification tool for Erlang programs that monitors system executions against formally specified correctness properties. It uses a logic-based specification language to define expected behaviors and dynamically checks these properties during program execution. In the scope of RESCALE, the pilot partner PST makes DetectEr usable for its embedded software (step 1) and generates formal models for checking specific pieces of software (step 2) running on embedded devices.

The development of DetectEr is currently still focused on step 1. Hence, a detailed evaluation of DetectEr with respect to technical requirements is currently not meaningful. It is expected that DetectEr can be integrated into the static code analysis module within the next three months, such that at least TR006, TR012, TR013, TR014 and TR016 will be covered in this time frame.

3.1.2.5 SASTER-cli

SASTER-cli is a command-line tool that performs static code analysis by using and orchestrating multiple static code analyzers. It supports a plethora of static code analyzers (e.g., Bandit, Semgrep, Flawfinder, etc.) and is designed for modularity and automation. The tool is capable of detecting software vulnerabilities across different programming languages and includes a ML component to reduce false positives.

TR004 Static code scanning:

The SASTER-cli tool fulfills the requirement for static code scanning by orchestrating multiple static code analyzers. The tool processes source code, runs the selected analyzers and aggregates their outputs in SARIF format.

SASTER-cli can be currently executed via the following command:

```
python3 saster-cli.py scan --offline -m
    Flawfinder,Bandit,Semgrep,Horusec,Bearer,Cppcheck -o results.sarif
    project/ --verbose
```

This command initiates analysis with the selected modules, with the results being in SARIF format. Each analyzer operates independently under the hood, and their outputs are later given as input to the SSCG Generator. Figure 3 shows the execution of the tool.

```
(kali@kali)~/Downloads/tool-saster-cli
└─$ python3 saster-cli.py scan --offline -m Horusec,Bandit,Flawfinder,Semgrep -o results.sarif project --verbose

[INFO] Module Bandit initialised successfully.
[INFO] Module Semgrep initialised successfully.
[INFO] Module Flawfinder initialised successfully.
[INFO] Module Horusec initialised successfully.
[INFO] Bandit version detected: bandit 1.7.10
python version = 3.12.6 (main, Sep 7 2024, 14:20:15) [GCC 14.2.0]
[INFO] Module Bandit loaded successfully.
[INFO] Semgrep version detected: 1.97.0
[INFO] Module Semgrep loaded successfully.
[INFO] Flawfinder version detected: 2.0.19
[INFO] Module Flawfinder loaded successfully.
[INFO] Horusec version detected: Version: v2.8.0
Git commit: df32c1ce03d2de748cecb76cff383f2851e198c3
Built: Wed Jun 08 13:57:08 2022
Distribution: normal
[INFO] Module Horusec loaded successfully.
[main] INFO profile include tests: None
[main] INFO profile exclude tests: None
[main] INFO cli include tests: None
[main] INFO cli exclude tests: None
[main] INFO running on Python 3.12.6
[INFO] Bandit analysis completed successfully.
[INFO] SARIF results saved to result_bandit.sarif.
[INFO] Flawfinder analysis completed successfully.
[INFO] SARIF results saved to result_flawfinder.sarif.
[INFO] Horusec analysis completed successfully.
[INFO] SARIF results saved to result_horusec.sarif.
[INFO] Semgrep analysis completed successfully.
[INFO] SARIF results saved to result_semgrep.sarif.
[INFO] All module scans completed.
```

Figure 3: Example Execution of the SASTER-cli Tool

TR005 False Positive/Negative analysis of static analysis report:

SASTER-cli supports the evaluation of static analysis accuracy by running multiple analyzers independently and generating a separate SARIF file for each tool. These individual outputs are then processed through a lightweight ML component designed to identify and reduce false positives. The ML component flags potentially irrelevant findings before results are passed to the SSCG.

Each SARIF output retains key metadata such as rule identifiers, severity levels and tool tags, allowing for precise filtering, cross-referencing and benchmarking. This structured output enables both manual review and automated evaluation.

TR006 Show the results of static analysis:

SASTER-cli outputs the results of multiple static code analyzers in SARIF format. This standardized output format includes detailed metadata such as detected issues, severity levels, rule identifiers (e.g., CWE/CVE) and tool name.

The SARIF files are then compiled using the SSCG Generator into the SSCG which is sent to the dashboard where the results can be viewed by the users.

For a concrete example of the output format generated by SASTER-cli, refer to Appendix E.

TR012 Tools/components should be able to “download and run”:

SASTER-cli is designed to be lightweight, portable and easy to deploy. It can be executed as a standalone tool using its docker image or within the Static Code Analysis Module. Users can

download the Docker image and immediately begin scanning source code with minimal setup.

TR013 Documentation Completeness:

SASTER-cli is accompanied by continuously updated documentation, hosted in the RESCALE internal SASTER-cli GitLab repository (restricted access to the consortium)¹. It includes step-by-step installation instructions, usage examples, supported modules, output configuration and debugging options.

The documentation ensures that users can install, configure and operate the tool independently, satisfying the requirement for comprehensive and accessible documentation.

TR014 Docker Compatibility:

SASTER-cli is fully compatible with docker-based execution environments. It is integrated into the Static Code Analysis Module docker image and has also been containerized independently.

This compatibility ensures portability across systems, simplifies deployment in CI/CD pipelines and fulfills the docker compatibility requirement. A standalone Docker image of SASTER-cli is also available through the RESCALE Harbor repository [19].

TR016 Automated Tool/Component Accessibility:

SASTER-cli supports automated execution via its CLI interface and can be easily integrated into scripts, pipelines or orchestration frameworks. All functionality is accessible via command-line arguments, allowing users to specify modules, output format and target directories. Logging verbosity and other runtime options are configurable.

This level of automation ensures that the tool can be triggered programmatically as part of broader validation workflows, satisfying the requirement for automated component accessibility.

TR018 Machine Readable Data Input/Output:

SASTER-cli produces output in the SARIF format, a widely adopted, machine-readable JSON schema, tailored for static analysis results. This ensures seamless integration with other RESCALE components such as the SSCG Generator.

The input to the tool consists of a standard directory structure containing source code files, while the output is structured SARIF files containing findings from all selected analyzers. For an example of the SARIF output structure from SASTER-cli, refer to Appendix E.

TR022 Modules-level ingesting of crucially important data sources:

SASTER-cli leverages the built-in capabilities of its integrated analyzers to identify known vulnerabilities based on CVEs and CWEs. These tools use internal rule sets and vulnerability signatures that are regularly updated to detect specific classes of software weaknesses.

By orchestrating these analyzers, SASTER-cli indirectly supports CVE/CWE-driven scanning without requiring custom logic. This modular design allows SASTER-cli to stay aligned with industry-standard vulnerability taxonomies and adapt as analyzers update their detection rules.

¹<https://gitlab.rescale-project.eu/rescale/saster/>

TR029 Machine Learning Integration:

SASTER-cli includes an embedded ML component designed to assist with false positives. After collecting results from multiple static analyzers, each tool's findings are preserved in individual SARIF files. These outputs are then processed by an ML model that evaluates each record to predict whether it is a likely false positive.

This ML-assisted filtering improves result quality by flagging potentially irrelevant findings before final aggregation or downstream consumption. The integration of this mechanism demonstrates the direct use of ML within SASTER-cli and contributes to the broader RESCALE workflow of combining traditional and ML-enhanced vulnerability detection.

TR030 Language Support:

SASTER-cli supports static code analysis for multiple programming languages through its integrated analyzers. Some analyzers scan Python code, while others analyze C/C++ code.

The tool's modular architecture allows users to activate only the analyzers relevant to the programming languages in their project, providing both flexibility and extensibility. This multi-language capability satisfies the requirement for multi-language support in the static code analysis process.

3.1.2.6 IVEE

The Intelligent Vulnerabilities Exposure Engine (IVEE) is currently under development as a tool within the Static Code Analysis Module. It is designed to perform vulnerability detection by employing symbolic execution.

While IVEE is still under development and comprehensive evaluation across all KPIs has not yet been performed, an initial evaluation methodology has been defined in the context of formal verification under KPI1.3.

Initial prototypes are being validated on open-source codebases that contain known vulnerabilities. Compared to other tools in RESCALE, the IVEE distinguishes itself by focusing on symbolic execution to systematically explore execution paths and identify vulnerabilities that may depend on specific program states or input conditions. This approach enables deeper analysis of control-flow and logic-driven weaknesses that are often difficult to detect using traditional static analysis techniques. Integration into the Static Code Analysis Module is expected within the coming months, and the IVEE is expected to cover several key requirements, including TR004, TR006, TR014, TR018 and TR027.

3.1.3 KPI Indicators

This section summarizes KPIs and their status in relation to the Static Code Analysis Module. At this stage, the KPIs relevant for the Static Code Analysis Module have been identified, and for each KPI, the appropriate tool has been identified. The table 3 provides an overview of this process, listing each KPI (Title), the selected Tool that will be used for its assessment, the planned Validation Method, and the current Status. Currently, the tools and validation

approaches have been outlined and the status column reflects that these KPIs are currently in the preparation phase, with implementation and measurement planned for upcoming stages. The monitoring of KPIs will be conducted throughout the entire project to track progress and performance. However, the final evaluation of these KPIs will take place at the end of the project as part of Task 5.3 and will be documented in Deliverable 5.6.

Table 3: List of KPIs related to the Static Code Analysis Module

KPI	Title	Tool	Validation Method	Status
KPI1.2	Accuracy of security audits carried out within the project more than 95% for the specified use cases	SAVE-ME, SASTER-cli, IVEE, DetectEr	Evaluation measures based on precision	In progress
KPI1.3	Accuracy of cybersecurity testing methods in terms of formal verification more than 90% for known benchmark applications	IVEE, DetectEr	Evaluation measures based on precision (IVEE) and Manual validation (DetectER)	In progress
KPI2.1	Highly accurate vulnerability assessment algorithms more than 98% for known benchmark applications	SAVE-ME, SASTER-cli, IVEE	Evaluation measures based on precision	In progress
KPI2.2	Detect more than 90% of known vulnerabilities at the hardware and software level for the pilot's vulnerable hardware and software solutions	SAVE-ME, SASTER-cli, IVEE	Evaluation measures based on precision	In progress
KPI2.3	Detect at least two (2) unknown vulnerabilities	SAVE-ME, SASTER-cli, IVEE	Demonstration	In progress

KPI1.2 Accuracy of security audits carried out within the project more than 95% for the specified use cases:

This KPI measures the progress in developing and refining the static analysis tools for security auditing, evaluating its effectiveness in detecting vulnerabilities and weaknesses in a source code where the vulnerabilities are not known in advance. The goal is to achieve an accuracy of more than 95% for the specified use cases, ensuring reliable and actionable security assessments.

Accuracy in this context is defined as:

$$\frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (1)$$

where:

- TP (True Positives): Correctly identified vulnerabilities
- FP (False Positives): Incorrectly flagged vulnerabilities that do not actually exist

This evaluation measure is better known as *precision* in the ML community, and other measures that incorporate precision will also be considered. A benchmark analyzer is used to establish a reference accuracy level by running it on manually verified datasets where all issues are known.

This KPI will be monitored through the all tools included in the Static Code Analysis Module, but currently we designed evaluation strategy for SAVE-ME tool. A similar approach will be applied for other tools with selection of appropriate benchmark application.

In the case of SAVE-ME tool, the benchmark analyzer is InfERL output supervised by an Erlang expert. The SAVE-ME tool's accuracy is then computed using the same dataset, with the requirement that its performance must reach at least 95% of the benchmark tool's accuracy. To evaluate SAVE-ME's accuracy, a ground truth dataset of Erlang functions with labeled vulnerabilities is being developed. This dataset is generated using InfERL, a static analysis tool, to extract functions from real-world Erlang projects. The initial labels produced by InfERL will then be refined by manual inspection and expert validation to ensure accuracy and reduce false positives. Once finalized, this dataset will serve as a real-world benchmark for testing SAVE-ME's performance. The tool will be executed on the dataset, and its results will be compared with the verified ground truth, allowing the computation of TP and FP values. This evaluation will guide further refinements to improve SAVE-ME's precision and effectiveness in security audits.

KPI1.3: Accuracy of cybersecurity testing methods in terms of formal verification more than 90% for known benchmark applications

The IVEE is designed to verify whether a software component satisfies predefined security properties by applying symbolic execution to compiled binaries. The evaluation of IVEE focuses on its ability to correctly determine whether such properties hold or are violated, aligning with the objective of formal verification accuracy under KPI1.3.

To measure IVEE's effectiveness, compiled binary files containing known properties are used. These properties may include assertions about memory safety, control flow correctness or other critical behaviors. Each test file is associated with an expected outcome, either the property should be satisfied or a violation should occur. IVEE analyzes each binary and attempts to either verify the correctness of the properties or produce counterexamples for violations.

In addition to direct evaluation against expected outcomes, IVEE's results are also compared with the outputs of other tools that perform similar formal verification tasks using comparable methods. This comparative evaluation serves to further validate IVEE's correctness and reliability in detecting or verifying property-related behaviors.

The accuracy of IVEE is calculated using a standard classification formula, which considers four outcomes: True Positives (TP), when a real property violation is correctly detected; True Negatives (TN), when a property holds and IVEE correctly confirms it; False Positives (FP), when IVEE incorrectly flags a violation; and False Negatives (FN), when a real violation is missed. Accuracy in this context is defined as:

$$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (2)$$

where:

- TP (True Positives): Property violations correctly identified by IVEE
- TN (True Negatives): Properties that hold and are correctly confirmed by IVEE
- FP (False Positives): Properties that hold but are incorrectly flagged as violations
- FN (False Negatives): Actual property violations that were not detected by IVEE

This metric reflects how often IVEE produces the correct verification result, whether it confirms correctness or identifies a violation. Since KPI1.3 requires that the accuracy of formal verification methods exceed 90%, this percentage-based result provides a direct means of determining compliance with the KPI.

As the IVEE tool is still under development, both the evaluation methodology and the applied formula may be subject to change as the implementation matures.

DetectEr operates by evaluating software execution traces of Erlang software against user-defined formal models, typically specified in temporal logic. These formal models encapsulate expected system behaviors. When a trace violates a model, DetectEr reports a finding. This finding represents either a real defect in the code or a flaw in the model itself, requiring iterative refinement. Unlike traditional static or dynamic analyzers, DetectEr's results are inherently true positives once a valid model is in place, emphasizing the correctness of the model over generic bug detection. Since each confirmed violation under a validated model corresponds to a true bug, the tool inherently achieves high precision.

DetectEr's uniqueness lies in its reliance on user-defined formal models, making standardized benchmark applications inapplicable due to the inherently custom and context-specific nature of its analysis. Comparable tools do not exist for the Erlang programming language.

KPI2.1 Highly accurate vulnerability assessment algorithms more than 98% for known benchmark applications:

This KPI measures the accuracy of the static analysis tools in detecting vulnerabilities in known benchmark applications. The goal is to achieve an accuracy of more than 98%, ensuring that tools reliably identify security vulnerabilities in real-world and (synthetic) test scenarios.

This KPI will be monitored across all tools integrated into the Static Code Analysis Module. Currently, the evaluation strategy has been designed specifically for the SAVE-ME tool. A similar approach will be adopted for the remaining tools.

To systematically assess SAVE-ME's effectiveness, the evaluation follows these key steps:

1. A benchmark application is an application under test, where the vulnerabilities are already known. The benchmark application contains a predefined set of vulnerabilities, either based on an established knowledge base of known security issues or inserted through a structured vulnerability injection methodology.

2. Each benchmark application is analyzed using the InfERL tool guided by an Erlang expert.
3. The number of actual vulnerabilities present in the benchmark application is documented, providing a reference point for evaluation.
4. The assessment results from SAVE-ME are compared with the documented vulnerabilities, and the overall accuracy is computed as expressed in Eq. 1 and the following text. The goal for this metric is to exceed the average of 98% across all tested applications.

To evaluate SAVE-ME's performance, a set of benchmark applications will be utilized, where the vulnerabilities are manually or synthetically inserted and validated by security experts based on their knowledge. The module will be executed on these applications, and its results will be cross-referenced with the established ground truth.

Since SAVE-ME utilizes a DL-based vulnerability classification model, its performance will improve as the dataset used for training expands. The ongoing development of a labeled dataset of Erlang functions, generated using InfERL and refined through expert validation, will further enhance the accuracy of its vulnerability assessments.

KPI2.2: Detect more than 90% of known vulnerabilities at hardware and software level for the pilot's vulnerable hardware and software solutions

Rather than attempting to detect every possible vulnerability, the strategy involves defining a prioritized list of known vulnerabilities that are most relevant to the pilot's environment and ensuring that the tools, supported by manual verification where necessary, can detect 90% of them.

At present, a comprehensive assessment of all vulnerabilities in the pilots' software projects is not available. To address this, we will curate a representative subset of known vulnerabilities from relevant public databases (e.g., CVE) and known security issues associated with the software components used in the pilot. This subset will serve as a practical benchmark for evaluating the detection capabilities of RESCALE tools.

This approach ensures that the KPI remains meaningful and achievable while adapting to the practical constraints of the pilot's current state of knowledge.

Furthermore, the primary detection methods employed (static code analysis tools) are inherently targeted at software and are not applicable to hardware. The latter is covered by dynamic analysis tools.

KPI2.3: Detect at least two (2) unknown vulnerabilities

Currently, no new vulnerabilities have been detected using RESCALE static code analysis tools. After the static code scans are completed on the pilot projects using the final tools, all flagged issues should be carefully and manually reviewed and analyzed to determine whether they represent exploitable unknown vulnerabilities or false positives.

The project leverages a combination of traditional static analysis techniques and modern ML/DL-enhanced analyzers. While these advanced tools are primarily trained on known patterns, their learning-based nature provides the potential to identify anomalous or previously unclassified

code patterns. This opens the possibility—albeit a narrow one—for detecting previously unknown vulnerabilities that may not be captured by conventional rule-based tools.

Importantly, the tools in use are not narrowly tailored to specific vulnerability classes. Instead, they aim to provide broad coverage across a wide range of potential security issues. This general-purpose capability, combined with expert manual analysis, increases the chances of surfacing novel or overlooked vulnerabilities within the pilot systems.

3.2 Dynamic Testing Module

The Dynamic Testing Module identifies vulnerabilities across hardware, firmware, and software in the supply chain. It employs various testing techniques tailored to each component type, such as fuzzing, runtime instrumentation, and protocol testing. This module integrates hardware and software testing components to conduct dynamic assessments and report results to the State Management Module. More details about this module can be found in Deliverable 3.3.

3.2.1 Technical Requirements

Table 4 presents a mapping of relevant functional requirements to their implementation and performance results inside the Dynamic Testing Module. The Dynamic Testing Module currently consists of several tools (DSCG Generator, RAISE, EvoMaster, InSpectre Gadget, FATex and Dynamic Hardware Analyzer) and they are validated in order to check which requirements are fulfilled in this iteration of software development. Those assessments provide insights into the module’s effectiveness, accuracy, and efficiency in real-world scenarios.

Table 4: List of Initial Functional and Non-Functional Requirements related to the Dynamic Testing Module

TRID	Title	Tool	Validation method	Status
TR008	Flexible dynamic analysis applied to software/-firmware using multiple optimization techniques (classic, fuzzing and ML/DL based)	RAISE, EvoMaster	Demonstration	In progress
TR009	Dynamic analysis applied to hardware	InSpectre Gadget, Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Demonstration	Achieved
TR010	Show the results of dynamic analysis	EvoMaster, RAISE, FATex, InSpectre Gadget, Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Demonstration	Achieved

Table 4 – continued from previous page

TRID	Title	Tool	Validation method	Status
TR011	Generate DSCG	DSCG Generator	Demonstration	Achieved
TR012	Tools/components should be able to "download and run"	All included tools	Demonstration	Achieved
TR013	Documentation Completeness	All included tools	Demonstration	In progress
TR014	Docker Compatibility	All included tools	Demonstration	Achieved
TR016	Automated Tool/Component Accessibility	All included tools	Demonstration	In progress
TR017	Secure Communication Protocol Support	RAISE	Demonstration	In progress
TR018	Machine-Readable Data Input/Output	All included tools	Demonstration	In progress
TR022	Modules-level ingesting of crucially important data sources (CVE, etc.)	FATex	Demonstration	Achieved
TR031	Hardware Assessment Leakage Assessment metric	Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Demonstration	In progress
TR032	Device under Test Tailored Hardware Assessment	Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Demonstration	In progress
TR033	Hardware Assessment Trace Collection speed	Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Demonstration	In progress
TR034	Remote Side Channel Trace Collection	Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Demonstration	In progress
TR035	Hardware Security Assessment Reporting	Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Demonstration	In progress
TR047	Low-level Hardware Assessment – Exploitability	InSpectre Gadget	Demonstration	In progress
TR048	Low-level Hardware Assessment – Targets	InSpectre Gadget	Demonstration	Achieved
TR049	Low-level Hardware Assessment – Analysis Time	InSpectre Gadget	Demonstration	Achieved
TR050	Low-level Hardware Assessment – Reporting	InSpectre Gadget	Demonstration	Achieved

3.2.2 Evaluation Results

In the following section, the evaluation results for each identified tool will be presented, demonstrating how each tool contributes to the validation of the defined requirements.

3.2.2.1 DSCG Generator

The DSCG Generator is designed to streamline the processing of test reports from multiple dynamic testing analysis tools. It consolidates these reports into a single DSCG, formatted as a CycloneDX document, ensuring standardized and efficient data representation. Once generated, the DSCG is transmitted to the RESCALE platform, leveraging key configuration parameters such as a URL endpoint, authentication token, a list of integrating tools, and a shared volume for seamless communication between multiple containers or tools.

TR011 Generate DSCG:

The DSCG Generator is responsible for collecting reports from dynamic analyzer tools, ensuring that all Dynamic Testing Modules/Tools provide data in a common, machine-readable format. It integrates essential details from these reports, retrieves relevant information from SSCG, and ingests DSCG data from various analysis modules. By processing and standardizing this information according to the common DSCG format specification, the DSCG Generator produces the final, unified DSCG report.

TR012 Tools/components should be able to "download and run":

The Dockerized version of the DSCG Generator are accessible via the [Rescale Harbor repository](#) and available for all RESCALE users to download and run. Pilot owners can already achieve this by downloading the DSCG Generator image from the Rescale Harbor and running it within their own pilot environment.

TR013 Documentation Completeness:

As the tool develops, its documentation is consistently revised and enhanced. Additionally, we provide straightforward and comprehensive Docker documentation.

TR014 Docker Compatibility:

The DSCG Generator is built on Docker and is created and executed using Docker commands.

Before using the DSCG Generator, users must ensure the following resources are prepared:

- Required Files:
 - wrapper.py
 - Dockerfile
 - sscg.json
- Shared Data Volume:
 - Ensure the shared-data volume used by the analyzer tool's Docker container is available. This volume is mounted using the `-v shared-data:/output` option.

The user needs to download the Docker image from Rescale Harbor and then run the downloaded container with the necessary environment variables and shared volume, for example:

```
docker run --rm -it -v $(pwd)/output:/output -e
  SSCG_UID="bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3164f9cd1093" -e
  AUTH_TOKEN="myToken" -e
  RESCALE_URL="https://sm.dev.rescale-project.eu"
  harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/dscg-generator:latest --tools-list
  "evomaster,raise"
```

Once the container completes processing, if needed, copy the generated output to your local system using:

```
docker cp <container_id>:/output/. $(pwd)/output
```

TR018 Machine-Readable Data Input/Output:

The DSCG Generator takes the DSCG portion of the analyzer tool's output (in JSON format) along with SSCG as input (in CycloneDX format) and produces output in CycloneDX format. The example showcasing the DSCG output, which is generated by integrating reports from two dynamic analyzer tools, RAISE and EvoMaster can be found in Appendix C.

3.2.2.2 RAISE

RAISE is a tool developed to improve REST API fuzzing by adding a custom genetic algorithm to RESTler. It makes use of RESTler's existing request structure and combines it with smarter search strategies. The goal is to increase the precision and coverage of tests, making it easier to find more complex vulnerabilities in web APIs.

TR008 Flexible dynamic analysis applied to software/firmware using multiple optimization techniques (classic, fuzzing and ML/DL based):

RAISE is a stateful REST API fuzzer, based on RESTler [1] in the process of being enhanced with genetic algorithms.

An adaptive fuzzing framework that dynamically adjusts test cases based on real-time feedback is implemented. As the fuzzer explores different API paths, it will refine and prioritize the most promising mutation strategies to maximize code coverage and trigger potential security vulnerabilities.

To achieve this, RAISE will integrate a machine learning model that leverages genetic algorithms to optimize fuzzing paths. Genetic algorithms will help in selecting, mutating, and evolving test cases by focusing on those that produce unexpected responses, increase API coverage, or expose security vulnerabilities. The fuzzing process will be designed to evolve iteratively, where test cases leading to unique or critical responses will be given higher priority for further mutations.

RAISE requires a Swagger (OpenAPI) file as an input to construct fuzzing test cases. The Swagger file provides a structured definition of the API, including endpoints, request methods, parameters, expected data types, and constraints. By processing this file, RAISE can generate well-formed API requests while strategically mutating parameters to explore edge cases and uncover vulnerabilities.

TR010 Show the results of dynamic analysis:

RAISE categorizes the detected issues into bug buckets based on response patterns, failure types, and API behavior to easily prioritize and classify them. Here is the bug-bucketing classification:

- **Response Code-Based Categorization**

- **5XX Errors (Server Failures):** Indicate crashes, unhandled exceptions, or improper error handling in the API backend. Example: A fuzzed input causes an internal server error (500 response).
- **4XX Errors (Client-Side Failures):** Indicate authentication, authorization, or input validation weaknesses. Example: sending a request in which no optional fields are defined, but the server sends a Bad Request 400 message.
- **Unexpected 2XX Responses:** Occur when invalid inputs are incorrectly accepted by the API, indicating logic flaws. Example: Sending an invalid JSON body but still receiving a 200 OK response or an unauthenticated request bypasses access control and receives a 200 response instead of a 401.

- **Failure Type Categorization**

- **Authentication and Authorization Failures:** Occur when unauthorized access is granted.
- **Unhandled Exceptions and Server Crashes:** Caused by malformed requests, type mismatches, or boundary condition errors.
- **Schema Violations:** API responses that do not conform to the expected Open API/Swagger schema.

Once the bugs are categorized, RAISE provides reports in the CycloneDX format.

TR012 Tools/components should be able to "download and run":

The dockerized version of RAISE is available on [Rescale Harbor repository](#). Please see TR014 below for additional info.

TR013 Documentation Completeness:

As the tool evolves, the documentation is constantly being adjusted and updated. The tool has a concise Docker documentation.

TR014 Docker Compatibility:

Once the RAISE docker image is downloaded from RESCALE Harbor, it can be run simply with the standard docker command:

```
sudo docker run --rm --network=host \  
  -v "$(pwd)/app/input:/app/input" \  
  -v "$(pwd)/output:/output" \  
  -e SWAGGER_FILE_NAME="swagger.json" \  
  -e AUTH_TOKEN="myAuthToken" \  
  -e SSCG_UID=SSCGSerialId \  
  \
```

```
-e RESCALE_URL="https://rescale.org" \  
raise "python /app/raise.py swagger.json /app/input /app"
```

The Docker file has the following environment variables that can be adjusted:

- TOOL_INPUT_DIR - is the path to the directory where the Swagger file is stored,
- SWAGGER_FILE_NAME - is the name of the Swagger file,
- TOOL_NAME - is the tool name (eg., raise).

TR017 Secure Communication Protocol Support:

RAISE inherited security communication protocols TLS 1.2+ and HTTPS from RESTler. It has an option `-token` via the command line for the Bearer token.

TR018 Machine-Readable Data Input/Output

RAISE uses a Swagger specification as input (see TR008 for RAISE), and the output is in JSON format (see TR010 for RAISE).

Example of RAISE's output:

```
"claims": [  
  {  
    "bom-ref": "Claim: RAISE found 6 instances of 500 errors!",  
    "evidence": [  
      "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at  
        /api/blog/posts/189",  
      "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at /api/blog/posts",  
      "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at /api/blog/posts",  
      "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at /api/blog/posts",  
      "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at /api/blog/posts"  
    ]  
  }  
]
```

```
"evidence": [  
  {  
    "bom-ref": "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at  
      /api/blog/posts/189",  
    "description": "Evidence gathered by RAISE for 500",  
    "data": [  
      {  
        "name": "RAISE Gadget Output",  
        "contents": {  
          "attachment": {  
            "contentType": "application/json",  
            "encoding": "base64",  
            "content": "ewogICJyZXF1ZXN0IjogewogICAgIlJlcXVlc..."  
          }  
        }  
      ]  
    }  
  ]
```

```
    }  
  ]  
}  
]
```

Also, RAISE is planned to categorize errors and use Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE).

3.2.2.3 FATex

The Firmware Analysis Toolkit (FAT) is a powerful tool designed to automate firmware analysis and emulation for embedded devices. It leverages QEMU [16] for emulation and Binwalk [11] for firmware extraction, enabling researchers and security professionals to analyze firmware without requiring physical hardware. This approach simplifies vulnerability detection and firmware reverse engineering.

TR010 Show the results of dynamic analysis:

FATex is a completely redesigned and improved version of FAT, incorporating automated supply chain analysis along with vulnerability mapping and detection. Once the firmware is emulated through QEMU, FATex retrieves the vulnerability data related to the firmware's binary files/executables via an OpenAPI and cross-references it with the CVE database. It extracts firmware binary images, identifies third-party libraries and binaries within the image, and checks for known vulnerabilities associated with these components. All identified vulnerabilities are then compiled into a DSCG report, enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of firmware security analysis with a special focus on software supply-chain visibility.

TR012 Tools/components should be able to "download and run":

The Dockerized version of the FATex is accessible via the [Rescale Harbor repository](#) and available for all RESCALE users to download and run. FATex is easy to execute on a given binary, with the default target configuration as follows:

USAGE:

```
fatex --firmware <firmware_path> --testcase <testcase_type>
```

OPTIONS:

- -f, --firmware Path to the firmware file.
- -t, --testcase [Possible values: network, binary] – Specifies the type of test case.
- -v, --verbosity Displays detailed step-by-step output and more specific error messages.
- -h, --help Displays the help information.
- -V, --version Shows the version of FATex.

EXAMPLE:

```
$ fatex -f /app/my_firmware.tar -t binary
```

This requirement has been fulfilled by pilot owners through downloading the FATex image from the Rescale Harbor and deploying it within their respective pilot environments.

TR013 Documentation Completeness:

As the tool develops, its documentation is consistently revised and enhanced. Additionally, we provide straightforward and comprehensive Docker documentation. The complete documentation can be found at <https://gitlab.rescale-project.eu/rescale/dyn-fatex>.

TR014 Docker Compatibility:

FATex is built on Docker and, after being downloaded from Rescale Harbor, is executed using Docker commands.

```
docker run --rm -it -v $(pwd)/input:/input -v shared-data:/output -e
SSCG_UID="urn:uuid:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3164f9cd1093" -e
FASTCVE_URL="http://fastcve:8000" --network binare-network
harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/fatex_image:latest --verbose fatex -f
/input/WNAP320_V2.0.3_firmware.tar -t binary
```

TR018 Machine-Readable Data Input/Output:

FATex processes standard firmware image binaries (e.g., .bin), making them machine-readable. The output is generated in JSON format, following the template below, which includes the declarations field:

```
"declarations":{
  "claims":[
    {
      "bom-ref":"Claim: ReSCALE Test Suite FATex binaries",
      "evidence":["Evidence: binaries found", "Evidence: vulnerabilities
        identified","Evidence: FastCVE output"]
    }
  ],
  "evidence":[
    {
      "bom-ref":"Evidence: binaries found",
      "description":"Base64 representation of FATex binary check.",
      "data":[
        {
          "name":"ReSCALE Test Suite FATex output",
          "contents":{
            "attachment":{
              "contentType":"application/json",
              "encoding":"base64",
              "content":"W3sibmFtZSI6ImZpcm13YXJlLXVwZ3Jh..."
            }
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

```

    ]
  },
  {
    "bom-ref": "Evidence: FastCVE output",
    "description": "Base64 representation of FATex binary check with
      FastCVE output.",
    "data": [
      {
        "name": "ReSCALE Test Suite FATex + FastCVE output",
        "contents": {
          "attachment": {
            "contentType": "application/json",
            "encoding": "base64",
            "content": "W3sibmFtZSI6ImZpcm13YXJlLXVwZ3..."
          }
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "bom-ref": "Evidence: vulnerabilities identified",
    "description": "Base64 representation of FATex found vulnerabilities
      in CycloneDX format.",
    "data": [
      {
        "name": "ReSCALE Test Suite FATex vulnerability output",
        "contents": {
          "attachment": {
            "contentType": "application/json",
            "encoding": "base64",
            "content": "eyJ2dWxwZXJhYmlsaXRpZXMiO1t7ImJvbS1y..."
          }
        }
      }
    ]
  }
]
}

```

TR022 Modules-level ingesting of crucially-important data sources (CVE, etc): The tool analyzes the following vulnerabilities as part of its output format:

```

{
  "vulnerabilities": [
    {
      "bom-ref": "vuln-cve-2011-2716",
      "id": "CVE-2011-2716",
      "source": {
        "name": "NVD"
      },
      "description": "The DHCP client (udhcp) in BusyBox before 1.20.0 allows
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    remote DHCP servers to execute arbitrary commands via shell
    metacharacters in the (1) HOST_NAME, (2) DOMAIN_NAME, (3)
    NIS_DOMAIN, and (4) TFTP_SERVER_NAME host name options.",
  "affects": [
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:a:busybox:busybox:1.18.4:*:*:*:*:*:*:*"
    },
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:a:busybox:busybox:1.3.2:*:*:*:*:*:*:*"
    },
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:a:busybox:busybox:1.11.3:*:*:*:*:*:*:*"
    },
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:a:busybox:busybox:1.0.0:pre4:*:*:*:*:*:*"
    }
  ],
  "cwes": [
    20
  ]
},
{
  "bom-ref": "vuln-cve-2011-5325",
  "id": "CVE-2011-5325",
  "source": {
    "name": "NVD"
  },
  "description": "Directory traversal vulnerability in the BusyBox
    implementation of tar before 1.22.0 v5 allows remote attackers to
    point to files outside the current working directory via a symlink.",
  "affects": [
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:o:debian:debian_linux:8.0:*:*:*:*:*:*"
    },
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:o:canonical:ubuntu_linux:18.04:*:*:*:lts:*:*"
    },
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:o:debian:debian_linux:9.0:*:*:*:*:*:*"
    },
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:o:canonical:ubuntu_linux:16.04:*:*:*:lts:*:*"
    },
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:o:canonical:ubuntu_linux:18.10:*:*:*:*:*:*"
    },
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:a:busybox:busybox:*:*:*:*:*:*"
    },
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:o:canonical:ubuntu_linux:14.04:*:*:*:esm:*:*"
    }
  ]
}

```

```
],
  "cwes": [
    22
  ],
  "ratings": [
    {
      "score": 7.5,
      "severity": "high",
      "method": "CVSSv31",
      "vector": "CVSS:3.1/AV:N/AC:L/PR:N/UI:N/S:U/C:N/I:H/A:N",
      "source": {
        "name": "NVD"
      }
    }
  ]
},
,
{
  "bom-ref": "vuln-cve-2019-11072",
  "id": "CVE-2019-11072",
  "source": {
    "name": "NVD"
  },
  "description": "lighttpd before 1.4.54 has a signed integer overflow,
  which might allow remote attackers to cause a denial of service
  (application crash) or possibly have unspecified other impact via a
  malicious HTTP GET request, as demonstrated by mishandling of /%2F?
  in burl_normalize_2F_to_slash_fix in burl.c. NOTE: The developer
  states \"The feature which can be abused to cause the crash is a new
  feature in lighttpd 1.4.50, and is not enabled by default. It must
  be explicitly configured in the config file (e.g. lighttpd.conf).
  Certain input will trigger an abort() in lighttpd when that feature
  is enabled. lighttpd detects the underflow or realloc() will fail
  (in both 32-bit and 64-bit executables), also detected in lighttpd.
  Either triggers an explicit abort() by lighttpd. This is not
  exploitable beyond triggering the explicit abort() with subsequent
  application exit.",
  "affects": [
    {
      "ref": "cpe:2.3:a:lighttpd:lighttpd:*:*:*:*:*:*:*"
    }
  ],
  "cwes": [
    190
  ],
  "ratings": [
    {
      "score": 9.8,
      "severity": "critical",
      "method": "CVSSv3",
      "vector": "CVSS:3.0/AV:N/AC:L/PR:N/UI:N/S:U/C:H/I:H/A:H",
```

```
        "source": {
          "name": "NVD"
        }
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

3.2.2.4 Dynamic Hardware Analyzer

The Dynamic Hardware Analyzer is a versatile tool designed to enhance hardware security by identifying and mitigating vulnerabilities through advanced analysis techniques, including side-channel attacks on FPGAs. It is particularly effective in testing across various hardware platforms and components, ensuring accurate and efficient security assessments.

TR009 Dynamic analysis applied to hardware:

The Dynamic Hardware Analyzer tool enables testing across various hardware platforms and components, applying advanced analysis techniques such as Correlation Power Analysis (CPA), Test Vector Leakage Assessment (TVLA) or various ML-based attacks to extract and evaluate side-channel information. By leveraging multiple sensing and measurement methods, it detects transient vulnerabilities, power fluctuations, and timing anomalies across different architectures. This comprehensive approach ensures accurate and efficient hardware security assessments, adapting to the unique characteristics of each tested device.

TR010 Show the results of dynamic analysis:

After the analysis is completed, a JSON report is generated that contains all the target information and the attack executed by the Analyzer, bundled with the possible vulnerabilities detected based on the specific configuration. The report is visible and can be read either when the user performs DRY_RUNs (i.e., the tool is tested locally and no results are posted to the Rescale URL.), as demonstrated in D5.3, or after the final analysis. After a brief compatibility transformation through a custom script, it is passed on to the DSCG generator which incorporates the analysis result in the final DSCG output and can be viewed either through the Dashboard or by downloading the final TBOM.

TR012 Tools/components should be able to "download and run":

The container offering the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer functionality is available on [Rescale Harbor repository](#) for the Consumer to execute on their local system as an individual container within the Dynamic Analysis module during the Dynamic Analysis.

TR013 Documentation Completeness:

The existing documentation currently describes straightforwardly the functionality offered through the Docker container. Any additional features or attacks that will be available by the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer will be properly documented.

TR014 Docker Compatibility:

The trace analysis functionality of the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer is implemented in Docker and is fully accessible through Docker commands. Prior to execution, the security expert is needed to provide an `attack_config.json` file that describes the type of the attack and its relevant files, as well as correctly mounting the data volume containing them.

User first needs to download the docker image from RESCALE Harbor, Then, for execution using the RESCALE wrapper, employing the following command:

```
docker run -it --rm \  
-v $(pwd)/output:/output \  
-v $(pwd)/trace_analyzer:/app/io/inputs/attacks \  
-e AUTH_TOKEN="myToken" \  
-e SSCG_UID="urn:cdx:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3134f8cd1092" \  
-e RESCALE_URL="https://rescale.org" \  
sca_trace_analyzer:ubuntu2204
```

In the non-interactive mode (default behaviour), the user can select an attack configuration file to launch the attack and save the report to the chosen output directory. When the container is running, you can execute a sample attack with:

```
docker exec sca_trace_analyzer:ubuntu2204 python3 trace_analyzer/main.py \  
--config-file io/inputs/attacks/attack_config.json --output-dir \  
$TOOL_OUTPUT_DIR
```

TR018 Machine-Readable Data Input/Output:

The inputs for the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer are machine-readable. Initiation of the analysis is implemented with a JSON configuration file, while the various traces needed for the side channel analysis are usually in various machine-readable file formats like `.csv`, `.mat` or `.bit`. The output is a machine-readable JSON output, which is read and integrated into the final DSCG. Examples of input and output for the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer can be seen in sections 3.3.3.1 and 3.3.3.2, respectively of Deliverable D3.5.

TR031 Hardware Assessment Leakage Assessment metric:

Due to the nature of the side channel analysis field and the increased diversity of targets and algorithms, a unified or standardized approach to measure possible leakage has not been established universally. However, the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer employs a customized approach to reflect the leakage metric. This metric can vary depending on the type of attack executed and the underlying Device under Test (DuT), alternating between percentile or boolean values. As an example, a ML-based attack is inherently an accuracy metric in most cases. For any attack, the underlying metric used is translated to an approximate severity level (low, medium, high) for the vulnerability assessment to comply with the project's vulnerability report schema. Nevertheless, the security expert is required to have an understanding of the specific experiment to correctly assess the vulnerability status of the implementation.

TR032 Device under Test Tailored Hardware Assessment:

The hardware assessment process is tailored to the specific characteristics of the DuT, ensuring accurate and efficient side-channel evaluations. By adapting measurement techniques to the

DuT's architecture, power characteristics, and operational behavior, the system optimizes trace collection and analysis.

TR033 Hardware Assessment Trace Collection speed:

The hardware assessment trace collection process is optimized for high-speed acquisition using Time-to-Digital Converter (TDC) sensors, which enable precise and rapid measurement of side-channel leakage. By leveraging high-resolution timing analysis, the system ensures minimal overhead while capturing traces with nanosecond-level precision. Traces are collected at every hardware clock cycle, ensuring continuous and fine-grained monitoring of the device's behavior. To efficiently handle the high data throughput, a FIFO (First-In, First-Out) buffer is used as memory to store results before transmission, prevent data loss, and ensure smooth processing in high-speed environments.

TR034 Remote Side Channel Trace Collection:

The remote side-channel trace collector leverages TDC sensors to capture precise timing variations caused by power fluctuations and electromagnetic emissions in the target FPGA device. These TDC sensors enable high-resolution measurement of side-channel leakage, even in remote environments, by detecting subtle changes in signal propagation delays. The collected traces are then transmitted securely for analysis, allowing for efficient remote side-channel evaluations without requiring direct physical access to the hardware.

TR035 Hardware Security Assessment Reporting:

The Dynamic Hardware Analyzer outputs a report for each attack and transforms it into a JSON format. An example can be viewed below:

```
{
  "declarations": {
    "claims": [
      {
        "bom-ref": "Claim: SCA-Trace Analyzer Leakage Detected",
        "target": "pkg:hex/sca-report@1.0",
        "evidence": [
          "Moderate leakage detected with a possible risk of key
            recovery under certain conditions."
        ]
      }
    ],
    "evidence": [
      {
        "bom-ref": "Evidence: Leakage Metrics",
        "description": "Moderate leakage detected with a possible risk
          of key recovery under certain conditions.",
        "data": [
          {
            "contents": {
              "attachment": {
                "content":
                  "eyJzaWR1X2NoYW5uZWxfYXR0YWNrIjogeyJ0e..."
              }
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

```

    }
  }
]
},
"vulnerabilities": [
  {
    "bom-ref": "vuln-SCV-ML-RF",
    "id": "SCV-ML-RF",
    "description": "Moderate leakage detected with a possible risk of
      key recovery under certain conditions.",
    "ratings": [
      {
        "severity": "medium"
      }
    ]
  }
]
}
}

```

3.2.2.5 InSpectre Gadget

InSpectre Gadget is a program analysis tool written in Python that can be used to inspect potential Spectre disclosure gadgets. Tool performs generic constraint analysis and models knowledge of advanced exploitation techniques to accurately reason over gadget exploitability in an automated way. Whenever there is a chain of loads that can be executed in a speculative window, we might be able to leak memory through a side-channel. This tool finds potential Spectre gadgets and classifies them based on properties like where can we leak from, where can we place our reload buffer, etc. Given a binary and a list of speculation entrypoints, InSpectre Gadget will explore a configurable amount of basic blocks for each entrypoint and output a CSV with a list of all the transmission gadgets it found.

TR010 Show the results of dynamic analysis

InSpectre Gadget inspect potential Spectre disclosure gadgets and performing exploitability analysis. Since the focus is on the disclosure gadgets, the tool can possibly capture different Spectre variants (v1, v2, etc.). Within RESCALE, we specifically focus on Spectre v2. The output of the analysis is a report on the exploitable Spectre gadgets (of different types) found in the given program binary.

TR012 Tools/components should be able to "download and run":

The InSpectre Gadget tool can be downloaded from <https://github.com/vusec/inspectre-gadget/>. InSpectre Gadget is straightforward to run on a given binary with the default target set:

```

- Usage: inspectre <BINARY>

- Example:
  $ inspectre ./input/binary.so

```

TR013 Documentation Completeness:

The complete documentation can be found at <https://vusec.github.io/inspectre-gadget/>.

TR014 Docker Compatibility:

InSpectre Gadget provides full Docker support:

```
= $ docker run --rm -it \  
  -v $(pwd)/input:/input \  
  -v $(pwd)/output:/output \  
  -e AUTH_TOKEN="myAuthToken" \  
  -e SSCG_UID=SSCGSerialId \  
  -e RESCALE_URL="https://rescale.org" \  
  inspectre_image /app/inspectre /input/binary.so
```

TR018 Machine-Readable Data Input/Output:

The input binary is a standard (e.g., ELF) binary, thus machine-readable. The output format is JSON, with the following template:

```
{  
  "declarations": {  
    "claims": [  
      {  
        "bom-ref": "Claim: InSpectre Gadget found {num-gadgets} exploitable  
gadgets!",  
        "evidence": [  
          "Evidence: {evidence}"  
        ]  
      }  
    ],  
    "evidence": [  
      {  
        "bom-ref": "Evidence: {evidence}",  
        "description": "Evidence gathered by InSpectre Gadget",  
        "data": [  
          {  
            "name": "InSpectre Gadget Output",  
            "contents": {  
              "attachment": {  
                "contentType": "text/plain",  
                "encoding": "base64",  
                "content": "{base64-output}"  
              }  
            }  
          ]  
        }  
      ]  
    ],  
  ],  
}
```

TR022 Modules-level ingesting of crucially-important data sources (CVE, etc):

The tool reasons over the following vulnerabilities (part of the output format):

```
"vulnerabilities": [
  {
    "bom-ref": "vuln-cve-2024-2201",
    "id": "CVE-2024-2201",
    "source": {
      "name": "NIST"
    },
    "description": "A cross-privilege Spectre v2 vulnerability allows
      attackers to bypass all deployed mitigations, including the
      recent Fine(IBT), and to leak arbitrary Linux kernel memory on
      Intel systems.",
    "affects": [
      {
        "ref": "pkg:hex/input-binary"
      }
    ],
    "ratings": [
      {
        "score": 4.7,
        "severity": "Medium",
        "method": "CVSSv3",
        "vector": "CVSS:3.1/AV:L/AC:H/PR:L/UI:N/S:U/C:H/I:N/A:N"
      }
    ]
  }
]
```

3.2.2.6 EvoMaster

EvoMaster (integrated with FuzzDB) combines automated REST API testing with a comprehensive repository of security payloads. EvoMaster uses search-based and evolutionary testing to explore API behaviors, while FuzzDB provides known attack vectors (e.g., SQLi, XSS, command injection). This integration enables intelligent fuzzing and vulnerability detection, enhancing both functional and security testing capabilities in black-box and gray box testing.

TR008 Flexible dynamic analysis applied to software/firmware using multiple optimization techniques (classic, fuzzing and ML/DL based):

EvoMaster is the core component in the API fuzzing tool, which is designed and being implemented for security testing and includes a novel integration of three tools(EvoMaster, FuzzDB, coverage.py) and ML models. It has several algorithms implemented, which can be chosen depending on the type of testing. It supports black-box and white-box testing using Evolutionary Algorithms enhanced with Adaptive Hypermutation. FuzzDB is a dictionary of attack patterns and primitives for black-box application fault injection and resource discovery. It is being integrated with EvoMaster. The integration of EvoMaster with the FuzzDB payload repository and the use of ML for fuzzing vector evolution in black-box mode will provide flexibility and optimization techniques to expose unexpected responses and security vulnerabilities.

TR010 Show the results of dynamic analysis

The output of EvoMaster fuzzing on a REST API consists of various artifacts that help analyze the testing process and its findings. The results are categorized into several key components:

1. Discovered Issues & Bugs

EvoMaster detects unexpected responses and potential vulnerabilities.

- HTTP Errors: (e.g., 500 Internal Server Error, 400 Bad Request)
- Assertion Violations: When an expected output does not match actual behavior
- Unhandled Exceptions: Indicating robustness issues in the API
- Performance Issues: Such as slow responses or excessive memory usage

2. Test Cases (JUnit/Python)

EvoMaster generates automated test cases in formats such as **JUnit (Java/Kotlin)** or **Python scripts**, which can be used for regression testing. These test cases reproduce the API calls that were found to trigger issues or cover edge cases.

3. Security Findings

If EvoMaster is used in security testing mode, it may report:

- Injection vulnerabilities (e.g., SQLi, XSS)
- Authorization bypass
- Broken authentication issues
- Exposed sensitive data

These findings are linked to **FuzzDB payloads**.

4. Logs & Execution Reports

A summary report is created and included in the output of the tool. This report contains pieces of information such as: detected issues analyzing the schema, consumed search budget, number of covered targets, evaluated tests and evaluated actions, timestamps of API calls, needed budget (percentage of running time), passed time, potential faults and a number of test cases in a python script that can be used to reproduce the faults.

All this running information is concluded in a report, which is consumed by the DSCG generator. The report is in json format and contains elements compatible with part of Cyclone DX standard. These elements will be included in the final DSCG.

TR012 Tools/components should be able to "download and run":

The tool and its components can be easily downloaded from the Gitlab repository of the RESCALE project or from the harbor image repository. Running the tool is simple and environment-independent as it is containerized. The command for pulling the image from RESCALE harbor repository is:

```
docker pull harbor.rescale-project.eu/wp3/evomaster_image:latest
```

TR013 Documentation Completeness:

The existing documentation of the tool is being updated in parallel with the process of implementing its final version. There is also documentation in Gitlab that describes the use of the docker container.

TR014 Docker Compatibility:

The tool is containerized and can be run alone or as part of an integrated workflow. The container can be run with the command that follows and contains the minimum parameters needed by the tool. The command is written for the Windows environment.

```
docker run -it --rm ^
-v .\output:/output --network=host ^
-e AUTH_TOKEN="myToken" ^
-e SSCG_UID="urn:cdx:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3134f8cd1092" ^
-e RESCALE_URL="https://rescale.org" ^
-e DRY_RUN="false" ^
-e AUTH_HEADER="bearer myToken" ^
-e SUT_URL="http://192.168.2.2:5000/openapi" ^
-e MAX_TIME="5s" ^
--name emCont evomaster_image
```

TR018 Machine-Readable Data Input/Output:

The basic input required for EvoMaster to run on a REST API is an OpenAPI/Swagger specification in JSON format, describing the API endpoints, request parameters, and responses. The output of the tool is a JSON file in CycloneDX format.

Example:

```
{
  "declarations": [
    {
      "claims": [
        {
          "bom-ref": "urn:cdx:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3134f8cd1092",
          "evidence": [
            "Evidence: Faulty endpoints"
          ]
        }
      ],
      "evidence": [
        {
          "bom-ref": "urn:cdx:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3134f8cd1092",
          "description": "Faulty endpoints",
          "data": [
            {
              "name": "RescTest_faults_Test.py",
              "contents": {
                "attachment": {
                  "content": "zWyJjb250ZW50LXR..."
                }
              }
            }
          ]
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

```

    }
  ]
},
{
  "bom-ref": "urn:cdx:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3134f8cd1092",
  "description": "Summary report",
  "data": [
    {
      "name": "Summary report",
      "contents": {
        "attachment": {
          "content": "tYXNOZXIub3JnG1swbSB0byBsZWYybi..."
        }
      }
    }
  ]
}
],
"vulnerabilities": [
  {
    "id": "test_0_with500",
    "source": {
      "name": "Evo Master"
    },
    "affects": [
      {
        "ref": "/ping"
      }
    ],
    "description": "# (500) GET:/ping",
    "detail": "# Found 2 potential faults. Type-codes: 100, 200",
    "ratings": [
      {
        "severity": "unknown"
      }
    ],
    "recommendation": "Reproduce the test using the code in the
      evidence content item."
  }
]
}

```

The use of CWE categorization of the errors is in progress.

3.2.3 KPI Indicators

This section summarizes KPIs and their status in relation to the Dynamic Testing Module and the tools it incorporates.

Table 5: List of KPIs related to the Dynamic Testing Module

KPI	Title	Tool	Validation Method	Status
KPI1.2	Accuracy of security audits carried out within the project more than 95% for the specified use cases	RAISE, EvoMaster, InSpectre Gadget, FATex, Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Evaluation measures based on precision	In progress
KPI2.1	Highly accurate vulnerability assessment algorithms more than 98% for known benchmark applications	RAISE, EvoMaster, InSpectre Gadget, FATex, Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Evaluation measures based on precision	In progress
KPI2.2	Detect more than 90% of known vulnerabilities at hardware and software level for the pilot's vulnerable hardware and software solutions	RAISE, EvoMaster, InSpectre Gadget, FATex, Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Detection results based on dynamic analysis	In progress
KPI2.3	Detect at least two (2) unknown vulnerabilities	RAISE, EvoMaster, InSpectre Gadget, FATex, Dynamic Hardware Analyzer	Detection results based on dynamic analysis	Discovered 2+ vulnerabilities (4 CVEs and counting)

KPI1.2 Accuracy of security audits carried out within the project more than 95% for the specified use cases:

This KPI will be monitored across all tools integrated into the Dynamic Testing Module. Currently, the evaluation strategy has been designed specifically for the RAISE and EvoMaster tool. A similar approach will be adopted for the remaining tools.

To ensure reliable security assessments, RAISE and EvoMaster will utilize an accuracy metric known as *precision* defined as:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3)$$

where:

- **TP (True Positives):** Correctly identified API vulnerabilities.
- **FP (False Positives):** Incorrectly flagged vulnerabilities that do not actually exist.

The development of RAISE requires the creation of a ground truth dataset containing labeled HTTP statuses that can indicate security issues. The verification process includes two key stages:

- **Genetic Algorithm Integration:** RAISE will prioritize high-impact fuzzing sequences by evolving test cases that maximize API coverage and exploit potential weaknesses.
- **Manual Review and Refinement:** Security experts will analyze flagged issues to reduce false positives and improve classification models.

As RAISE continues to be developed, its accuracy will be iteratively refined through AI-driven optimizations and continuous testing on real-world API datasets. The goal is to achieve and maintain a 95% or higher accuracy in detecting API security vulnerabilities. Once fully developed, RAISE will provide a state-of-the-art security auditing tool that significantly enhances REST API fuzzing through adaptive learning and intelligent test case generation.

The integration of EvoMaster with the FuzzDB repository improves the precision and effectiveness of automated security audits, ensuring that vulnerabilities are detected with a precision rate exceeding 95% for the specified use cases. This is achieved through a combination of intelligent test generation, comprehensive payload injection, and adaptive fuzzing techniques. The FuzzDB repository, a well-established collection of known attack vectors and security test payloads, is integrated into EvoMaster's fuzzing mechanism.

This allows the tool to:

- Inject malicious payloads (e.g., SQL injection, XSS, command injection) into API parameters.
- Simulate real-world attack scenarios to evaluate API resilience.
- Perform context-aware input mutation, refining test cases based on observed system behavior.

Using FuzzDB's structured data set, EvoMaster reduces **false negatives**, ensuring that security threats are thoroughly exposed.

Validation and metrics to ensure accuracy > 95%:

- False positives are minimized through multi-step verification of detected vulnerabilities.
- False negatives are reduced by iteratively refining test coverage using feedback-driven mutation.
- The precision and recall of security tests are continuously evaluated, maintaining an accuracy threshold above **95%**.

The precision-based formula is used to quantitatively ensure the accuracy of security audits. This tells you how many of the issues reported by EvoMaster are actual vulnerabilities.

EvoMaster will also use Recall metric defined as:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4)$$

where:

- **TP (True Positives):** Correctly identified API vulnerabilities.
- **FP (False Positives):** Incorrectly flagged vulnerabilities that do not actually exist.
- **FN (False Negative):** Real vulnerability that the tool failed to detect.

This indicates how many of the actual vulnerabilities were correctly found.

KPI2.1 Highly accurate vulnerability assessment algorithms more than 98% for known benchmark applications:

This KPI will be monitored across all tools integrated into the Dynamic Testing Module. Currently, the evaluation strategy has been designed specifically for the RAISE tool. A similar approach will be adopted for the remaining tools.

In the context of RAISE, this KPI measures the accuracy of the tool in detecting vulnerabilities in known benchmark applications. The goal is to achieve an accuracy of more than 98%, ensuring that the tool reliably identifies security vulnerabilities in real-world and synthetic test scenarios.

To systematically assess RAISE's effectiveness, the evaluation follows these key steps:

1. **Benchmark application:** An application under test, where the vulnerabilities are already known. The benchmark application contains a predefined set of vulnerabilities, either based on an established knowledge base of known security issues or inserted through a structured vulnerability injection methodology.
2. **Analysis using RAISE:** Each benchmark application is analyzed using RAISE's advanced fuzzing techniques, which incorporate genetic algorithms to improve the efficiency of security testing.
3. **Ground truth comparison:** The number of actual vulnerabilities present in the benchmark application is documented, providing a reference point for evaluation.
4. **Accuracy computation:** The assessment results from RAISE are compared with the documented vulnerabilities, and the overall accuracy is computed using standard precision-based metrics. The goal is to exceed an average accuracy of 98% across all tested applications.

To evaluate RAISE's performance, a set of benchmark applications will be utilized, where vulnerabilities are manually or synthetically inserted and validated by security experts. The module will be executed on these applications, and its results will be cross-referenced with the established ground truth.

Since RAISE utilizes a genetic algorithm-based fuzzing model, its performance will improve as the dataset used for optimization expands. The ongoing development of a labeled dataset of API vulnerabilities, generated using RESTler's fuzzing framework and refined through genetic selection, will further enhance the accuracy of its vulnerability assessments.

By continuously refining its mutation strategies and improving its benchmarking dataset, RAISE will be progressing toward achieving the target of 98% accuracy in vulnerability assessments across known benchmark applications.

KPI2.2 Detect more than 90% of known vulnerabilities at hardware and software level for the pilot's vulnerable hardware and software solutions:

This KPI will be monitored across all tools integrated into the Dynamic Testing Module but in this moment we have focused on identifying side-channel vulnerabilities across various platforms, including FPGA, CPU, and other hardware. We will validate this KPI across all available tools related to Dynamic Testing Module and report its status in the Deliverable D5.6.

The Hardware analyzer specifically tests for side-channel attacks, such as power analysis, electromagnetic emissions, and timing attacks, on these different platforms. We are in the process on identifying relevant CVEs if applicable and selecting side-channel attacks residing in the academic literature. By cross-referencing the hardware with known CVEs or relevant research works on side-channel attacks, we will be able to assess potential weaknesses and conduct empirical tests to detect side-channel leakage and related risks, ensuring thorough security analysis across the hardware and software. The component must have the ability to detect more than 90% of these selected CVEs (if applicable) or other known vulnerabilities from the literature, within the pilot environment.

KPI2.3 Detect at least two (2) unknown vulnerabilities:

The KPI highlights the discovery of significant security issues and multiple CVEs, showcasing the project's contribution to advancing security research. Currently, InSpectre Gadget has already identified more than 2 potential vulnerabilities. Other tools from Dynamic Testing Module will be applied to further evaluate this KPI and potentially uncover more unknown vulnerabilities.

InSpectre Gadget focused on identifying microarchitectural vulnerabilities in modern computing architectures. Key achievements include:

- **SLAM:** Discovery of a new covert channel amplifying the impact of Spectre attacks on CPUs supporting Intel LAM, exposing vulnerabilities in noncanonical address translation paths.
- **Spectre-MTE:** Identification of a new speculative oracle in ARM MTE-based solutions capable of disclosing tag assignments based on random tagging.
- **Native BHI:** First demonstration of native cross-privilege Spectre v2 attacks, resulting in [CVE-2024-2201](#) .
- **GhostRace:** Discovery of speculative race conditions, representing a novel class of speculative execution vulnerabilities, leading to [CVE-2024-2193](#) and [CVE-2024-26602](#).

3.3 TrustOR

TrustOR facilitates the generation, validation, and management of TBOMs by securely aggregating information from the Assessment Domain, including Software Bill of Materials (SBOM)s, Static Supply Chain component Guarantee (SSCG)s and Dynamic Supply Chain component Guarantee (DSCG)s. By establishing trusted references between these elements, TrustOR creates a cohesive security profile that can be verified and traced throughout the supply chain lifecycle.

3.3.1 Technical Requirements

The validation process for TrustOR focuses on assessing its capability to securely manage data which are prerequisites for TBOMs and provide reliable API access for stakeholders. The following table presents the technical requirements mapped to TrustOR's implementation, along with their validation methods and current status.

Table 6: List of Initial Functional and Non-Functional Requirements related to the TrustOR component

TRID	Title	Tool	Validation method	Status
TR001	The TBOM should be based on an existing BOM Standard Format	TrustOR	Demonstration	Achieved
TR002	The TBOM must have a well defined structure Format	TrustOR	Demonstration	Achieved
TR012	Tools/components should be able to "download and run"	TrustOR	Demonstration	Achieved
TR013	Documentation Completeness	TrustOR	Demonstration	In progress
TR014	Docker Compatibility	TrustOR	Demonstration	Achieved
TR015	OpenAPI-compliant API Documentation	TrustOR	Demonstration	Achieved
TR017	Secure Communication Protocol Support	TrustOR	Demonstration	Achieved
TR018	Machine-Readable Data Input/Output	TrustOR	Demonstration	Achieved
TR021	RESCALE common Storage Repository	TrustOR	Demonstration	Achieved
TR041	TBOM Life cycle management	TrustOR	Demonstration	In progress
TR042	TBOM Generation - prerequisites gathering	TrustOR	Demonstration	Achieved
TR043	TBOM Generation - merging information	TrustOR	Demonstration	Achieved
TR044	TBOM Generation - security & trust	TrustOR	Demonstration	In progress
TR045	TBOM Validation	TrustOR	Demonstration	In progress
TR046	TBOM Validation - check TBOM is up-to-date	TrustOR	Demonstration	In progress

3.3.2 Evaluation Results

TR012 - Tools/components should be able to "download and run":

As seen in Figure 4, the TrustOR component can be easily downloaded with the following Docker command:

```
docker pull harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/trustor:latest
```

and run with:

```
docker container run -it harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/trustor:latest
```

```

tgogos@PW04PWB:~$ docker pull harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/trustor:latest
latest: Pulling from rescale-all/trustor
7cf63256a31a: Already exists
21eb2f74e859: Already exists
2e61b3be9aca: Already exists
9a2c563c66ec: Already exists
08d706b09879: Pull complete
c94b1905ab9b: Pull complete
ecd313d56777: Pull complete
620f935ca149: Pull complete
Digest: sha256:f926da5d74875d298dbdf36cea35328c9c96364044981382cb6bff36f89883df
Status: Downloaded newer image for harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/trustor:latest
harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/trustor:latest
tgogos@PW04PWB:~$
tgogos@PW04PWB:~$
tgogos@PW04PWB:~$ docker container run -it harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/trustor:latest

FastAPI Starting production server 🚀

Searching for package file structure from directories with __init__.py files
WARNING ENV file: not found
INFO ENV variables: will be loaded from the system
WARNING ENV variables not already set: will use DEFAULT values where applicable
VERSION: 0.1.0
MONGO_USER: root
MONGO_PASS: pass
MONGO_HOST: mongodb
MONGO_PORT: 27017
MONGO_AUTH_SOURCE: admin
STATE_MANAGER_URL: http://state-manager:3000
SECURITY_ASSURANCE_SKIP: false
SECURITY_ASSURANCE_URL: https://rescale.sphynxlabs.net
SECURITY_ASSURANCE_USERUUID: 24e3b64e-db38-49d4-9b3e-2e0b9daa4d45
SECURITY_ASSURANCE_CLIENT_ID: assurancegui
SECURITY_ASSURANCE_USERNAME: rescale
SECURITY_ASSURANCE_PASSWORD: ██████████
BESU_URL: http://besu:8545
MONGODB_URI: mongodb://root:pass@mongodb:27017?authSource=admin
Importing from /code

module
└─ app
   ├── __init__.py
   └── main.py

code Importing the FastAPI app object from the module with the following code:

from app.main import app

app Using import string: app.main:app

```

Figure 4: TrustOR component downloaded and run with Docker CLI

TR013 - Documentation Completeness:

In Figure 5, part of TrustOR GitLab repository README.md is being displayed. These details are for helping a developer clone the repository, install the dependencies needed, build it and run it with either native Python or Docker.

The screenshot shows the README.md file for the TrustOR repository. It includes the following sections:

- TrustOR**: RESCALE Trust Orchestrator main repository.
- Setup guidelines**: For convenience we use `make`, but you can always take a look at the actual commands in our `Makefile`.
- Python**: (More suitable for local development) The steps below will help you prepare your virtual environment (`.venv`) and then `run` the FastAPI app. In case you need to change any configuration parameters, they are located in the `.env` file.
 - `make venv` # creates a Python virtual environment inside the "app" directory
 - `make install` # installs Python dependencies from the requirements.txt file
 - `make dotenv` # copies `.env.example` to `.env` (⚠ you might need to modify `.env`)
- Run...**
 - `make run` # runs the FastAPI application
 - `make run-dev` # runs the FastAPI application in development mode
- Docker**: (Run the FastAPI app inside a container). This can be used for development too, by using `make docker-run-dev` which spins-up the container with the appropriate `volume` setup and "hot-reload" enabled.
 - `make dotenv` # the `.env` file is needed with docker too
 - `make do-build` # builds a trustor image
 - `make do-run` # creates and runs a trustor container
 - `make do-logs` # displays the logs
 - `make do-stop` # stops the container
 - `make do-rm` # removes the container

Figure 5: Part of TrustOR repository README.md

TR014 - Docker Compatibility:

TR012 already demonstrates that TrustOR is Docker-compatible, in terms of utilization. Moving towards "multi-platform" Docker compatibility, the TrustOR Docker image is offered for two CPU architectures, `linux/amd64` and `linux/arm64` as it can also be seen in Figure 6, which is a screenshot from the image details stored in Harbor.

Figure 6: TrustOR image OS/ARCH details as displayed in Harbor

TR015 - OpenAPI-compliant API Documentation:

TrustOR is based on FastAPI [17], a modern, fast web framework for creating APIs with Python, which is built on top of Starlette [2] and includes built-in support for OpenAPI. In Figure 7, part of the generated TrustOR Swagger page is depicted, along with the openapi.json that contains the actual API specification.

Figure 7: TrustOR Swagger and OpenAPI json

TR017 - Secure Communication Protocol Support:

In Listing 1, part of the NGINX [14] configuration that is serving the RESCALE Development platform is provided. On the first server section, the reader can see the lines added by Certbot to set up the SSL certificates provided by Let's Encrypt [12], while on the last part, one can see the 301 Redirect definition for always redirecting to https://.

```
server {
    server_name sm.dev.rescale-project.eu;
    ...
    location /trustor/security_alerts {
        proxy_pass http://127.0.0.1:8000/api/security_alerts; # trustor service
        proxy_set_header Host $host;
        proxy_set_header X-Real-IP $remote_addr;
        proxy_set_header X-Forwarded-For $proxy_add_x_forwarded_for;
    }

    listen 443 ssl; # managed by Certbot
    ssl_certificate /etc/letsencrypt/live/dashboard.dev.rescale-project.eu/
fullchain.pem; # managed by Certbot
    ssl_certificate_key /etc/letsencrypt/live/dashboard.dev.rescale-project.eu/
privkey.pem; # managed by Certbot
    include /etc/letsencrypt/options-ssl-nginx.conf; # managed by Certbot
    ssl_dhparam /etc/letsencrypt/ssl-dhparams.pem; # managed by Certbot
}
server {
    if ($host = sm.dev.rescale-project.eu) {
        return 301 https://$host$request_uri;
    } # managed by Certbot

    listen 80;
    server_name sm.dev.rescale-project.eu;
    return 404; # managed by Certbot
}
```

Listing 1: Part from the NGINX configuration of the Dev Platform

TR018 - Machine-Readable Data Input/Output:

Figure 8 displays the Swagger documentation of TrustOR's data schemas, demonstrating the implementation of standardized data structures that satisfy requirement TR018. These clearly defined Pydantic models ensure all data exchanged with the component follows machine-readable formats, enabling automated processing by both internal and external systems.

Figure 8: Schema details as shown in TrustOR Swagger

TR021 - RESCALE common Storage Repository:

Figure 9 shows the Mongo Express [4] interface displaying the MongoDB [13] collections utilized by TrustOR, confirming compliance with requirement TR021. These database collections serve as the central storage mechanism for TBOM-related data, enabling persistent and structured storage of security assessment artifacts across the RESCALE platform.

The screenshot shows the Mongo Express interface for a database named 'rescale'. The 'Collections' section lists seven collections, each with 'View', 'Export', '[JSON]', 'Import', and 'Del' buttons. Below this is a 'Database Stats' table.

Database Stats	
Collections (incl. system.namespaces)	7
Data Size	13.1 KB
Storage Size	28.7 KB
Avg Obj Size #	2.19 KB
Objects #	6

Figure 9: MongoDB collections used by TrustOR, as seen via a Mongo Express dashboard

TR041 - TBOM Lifecycle Management:

Figure 10 shows a Swagger API request retrieving metadata for a specific TBOM identified by its serialNumber (urn:uuid:5bb1a08b-1216-4f0d-8d44-e303cf260c8c), demonstrating compliance with requirement TR041. The response's "logs" array, which is provided also at Listing 2, documents the sequential steps in the TBOM lifecycle, from initial creation through blockchain registration and Security Assurance integration, providing comprehensive traceability of the TBOM's status throughout its lifecycle.

```

...
"logs": [
  "STEP-0: TBOM serialNumber created",
  "STEP-1: TBOM creation started",
  "STEP-1: adding SBOM, SSCG & DSCG components",
  "STEP-1: BOV creation & validation: PASSED",
  "STEP-1: TBOM validation PASSED / STEP-1 finished",
  "STEP-2: TBOM added to blockchain",
  "STEP-3: Security assurance project created",
  "STEP-3: SBOM uploaded successfully to Security Assurance"
],
...

```

Listing 2: Part from TBOM metadata displaying TBOM lifecycle

Figure 10: Request / Response of endpoint for getting TBOM metadata

Figure 11 also gives the perspective of the TBOM lifecycle, as presented in the Deliverable 4.1 "Specification of TBOM Structure" in relation to these logs/steps. Steps 1 and 2 take place sequentially inside TrustOR component. Steps 3 and 4 are work in progress and occur asynchronously when the Security Assurance component submits a new Bill of Vulnerabilities (BOV). It is important to point out that every time a new BOV is submitted, steps 3 and 4 take place again. This practically means that TrustOR updates the TBOM's BOV, sets the potentially new severity level and then deprecates the old TBOM / adds the updated one by utilizing the relative functions provided by the Blockchain.

Figure 11: logs / steps mapped to the TBOM lifecycle introduced in D4.1

TR042 - TBOM Generation - prerequisites gathering:

Figure 12 displays TrustOR’s Swagger API endpoints dedicated to submitting the prerequisite security assessment artifacts (SBOM, SSCG, and DSCG) required for TBOM generation, satisfying requirement TR042.

Figure 12: TrustOR endpoints for receiving SBOMs, SSCGs & DSCGs

TR043 - TBOM Generation - merging information:

In the following json from Listing 3, which is a valid CycloneDX part of a TBOM example, the reader can notice the externalReferences to the related SBOM, SSCG and DSCG ur1s:

```

...
"components": [
{

```

```
"externalReferences": [
  {
    "comment": "Link to BOV",
    "type": "distribution",
    "url": "https://sm.dev.rescale-project.eu
/bovGet/urn:uuid:1b37a02f-1267-4f57-a2f3-2f8d0177996b"
  }
],
"name": "BOV",
"purl": "pkg:hex/grisp@2.6.0",
"type": "file"
},
{
  "bom-ref": "dscg-ref",
  "description": "a link to the DSCG of: grisp",
  "externalReferences": [
    {
      "comment": "DSCG URL",
      "type": "distribution",
      "url": "https://sm.dev.rescale-project.eu
/dscgGet/urn:uuid:3e671687-391b-41f5-a30f-a58921a69b78"
    }
  ],
  "name": "DSCG",
  "purl": "pkg:hex/a-very-nice-binary@1.0.0",
  "type": "file"
},
{
  "bom-ref": "sbom-ref",
  "description": "a link to the SBOM of: grisp",
  "externalReferences": [
    {
      "comment": "SBOM URL",
      "type": "distribution",
      "url": "https://sm.dev.rescale-project.eu
/sbomGet/urn:uuid:7b0ba9e7-d293-4d05-a923-9527728610b9"
    }
  ],
  "name": "SBOM",
  "purl": "pkg:hex/grisp@2.6.0",
  "type": "file",
  "version": "1"
},
{
  "bom-ref": "sscg-ref",
  "description": "a link to the SSCG of: grisp",
  "externalReferences": [
    {
      "comment": "SSCG URL",
      "type": "distribution",
      "url": "https://sm.dev.rescale-project.eu
```

```
    /sscgGet/urn:uuid:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3134f9cd1073"
  }
],
"name": "SSCG",
"purl": "pkg:hex/grisp@2.6.0",
"type": "file"
}
],
...
"dependencies": [
{
  "ref": "bov-ref"
},
{
  "ref": "dscg-ref"
},
{
  "ref": "sbom-ref"
},
{
  "ref": "sscg-ref"
},
{
  "dependsOn": [
    "bov-ref",
    "dscg-ref",
    "sbom-ref",
    "sscg-ref"
  ],
  "ref": "tbom1-metadata"
}
],
...
```

Listing 3: Part from TBOM displaying ref dependencies

TR044 - TBOM Generation - Security & Trust:

In Figure 13 the metadata of a Blockchain transaction is displayed. In particular they are related to TBOM with `serialNumber: urn:uuid:0495bf94-f202-4fb0-95d4-86f374b66091` and one can spot the hash of the TBOM object that was added to the blockchain as well as the `transactionHash` and the `blockNumber`.

Figure 14: Example of valid and not-valid TBOM

TR046 - TBOM Validation - check TBOM is up-to-date

With the current design, TR046 is also covered by TR045, since every security update coming from the Security Assurance component directly triggers the TBOM updating process, which practically includes the deprecation of the existing TBOM and the creation of a new, updated one. This way, active and valid TBOMs always include the latest updates, whereas outdated TBOMs are deprecated objects in the Blockchain and as a result, trying to validate them will return: False.

3.3.3 KPI Indicators

Table 7: List of KPIs related to the TrustOR Component

KPI	Title	Tool	Validation Method	Status
KPI3.1	Write at least 3 software and hardware TBOM entries in the RESCALE public blockchain	TrustOR	Demonstration	In progress
KPI3.2	Generate at least 3 software and hardware TBOM files	TrustOR	Demonstration	In progress
KPI3.3	Update and validate at least 3 software and hardware TBOM enabled applications	TrustOR	Demonstration	Preliminary stage

For KPIs 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3, the quantitative aspect are not yet be covered. At the current stage,

one test input has been used to demonstrate the functionality end-to-end. This serves as a proof-of-concept and confirms that the TrustOR component and the Trust Orchestrator framework can support addition of TBOMs with minimal overhead. The mechanism is in place, operational and more TBOMs can be added seamlessly once tooling from WP3 generates valid SBOMs, SSCGs and DSCGs for specific software or hardware components. To fully address this KPI, we are coordinating with pilot-partners to obtain TBOMs from at least two more applications. The infrastructure is ready to accommodate them, ensuring that the KPI targets can be met.

KPI3.1 - Write at least 3 software and hardware TBOM entries in the RESCALE public blockchain

In Figure 15 we see a test component on the left, that has an available TBOM, specifically with `serialNumber: urn:uuid:urn:uuid:d96c6a6c-5710-49f9-9335-04c5c33f06fd`. On the right, we see the information from TrustOR which reveals that it has been added to the blockchain, along with the relative metadata, like: the hash of the TBOM, the `transactionHash` and the `blockNumber`.

Figure 15: TBOM visible via Dashboard also added in the blockchain

KPI3.2 - Generate at least 3 software and hardware TBOM files

Figure 16 displays the TrustOR endpoint that returns a TBOM payload. This can easily be wrapped in a `.json` file and downloaded by a user via a browser application. For simplicity, this screenshot displays only a part of the TBOM but the reader can see the full TBOM at the appendix D.

Figure 16: Endpoint for receiving a TBOM file

KPI3.3 - Update and validate at least 3 software and hardware TBOM enabled applications

Figure 17 includes the validation part of this KPI. On the left, the endpoint for uploading and validating a TBOM is being demonstrated and on the bottom right, the returned result shows that the TBOM is valid. Provided a TBOM file, this endpoint looks up the TBOM serialNumber and (if found) compares them and then validates it against its hash in the blockchain.

Figure 17: Endpoint for validating a TBOM file

3.4 Ledger Infrastructure

Ledger Infrastructure is a blockchain-based platform that securely stores and manages TBOM integrity data in the form of hashes. By leveraging decentralized ledger technology, it creates an immutable record of TBOM components, SBOMs, SSCGs, and DSCGs. This setup ensures that any alterations to TBOM data are detectable through hash mismatches, providing a tamper-evident audit trail. The validation process for Ledger Infrastructure focuses on assessing its capability to securely store and verify TBOM hashes, ensuring reliable data integrity and stakeholder access throughout the supply chain lifecycle.

3.4.1 Technical Requirements

Table 8: List of Initial Functional and Non-Functional Requirements related to the Ledger Infrastructure component

TRID	Requirement Title	Component	Validation Method	Status
TR012	Tools/components should be able to "download and run"	Ledger Infrastructure	Deployment and accessibility tests	Achieved
TR013	Documentation Completeness	Ledger Infrastructure	Repository README.md	Achieved
TR014	Docker Compatibility	Ledger Infrastructure	Demonstration	Achieved
TR016	Automated Tool/Component Accessibility	Ledger Infrastructure	Demonstration	Achieved
TR017	Secure Communication Protocol Support	Ledger Infrastructure	Demonstration	Achieved
TR018	Machine-Readable Data Input/Output	RESCALE Framework	Demonstration	Achieved
TR019	Flexible choice of Ledger/Blockchain for integration	Ledger Infrastructure	Integration testing	In Progress
TR020	Decoupled blockchain deployment	Ledger Infrastructure	Architecture review	Achieved
TR036	Provide blockchain underlying infrastructure	Ledger Infrastructure	Assessment of blockchain environments	Achieved
TR037	Provide a homogeneous metrics for blockchain comparison	Ledger Infrastructure	Metrics evaluation	Achieved
TR038	Provide smart contracts deployment strategy	Ledger Infrastructure	Smart contract testing	Achieved
TR039	Smart contract data structure	Ledger Infrastructure	Data structure validation	Achieved

TR040	Implement strategies for bugs-free deployment of smart contracts	Ledger Infrastructure	Code review and testing	In progress
TR041	TBOM Life cycle management	Ledger Infrastructure	Lifecycle testing	In progress

3.4.2 Evaluation Results

TR012 - Tools/components should be able to "download and run":

As seen in Figure 18, the Ledger Infrastructure component can be easily downloaded with the following Docker command:

```
docker pull harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/besu:2025-02-11
```

and run with:

```
docker run -p 127.0.0.1:8545:8545 \
harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/besu:2025-02-11
```


Figure 18: Ledger Infrastructure component downloaded and run with Docker CLI

TR013 - Documentation Completeness:

Documentation for the Ledger Infrastructure component, including its configurations and deployment details, can be found in the README.md file under RESCALE's Trust Storage GitLab repository.

Figure 19: Example of README.md file from the RESCALE GitLab repository

TR014 - Docker Compatibility:

As already demonstrated by TR012, the Ledger Infrastructure component is fully compatible with the Docker environment. The Ledger Infrastructure specifically utilizes a dockerized image of Hyperledger BESU [8].

Figure 20: Ledger Docker image based on Hyperledger Besu available in RESCALE Harbor registry.

TR016 - Automated Tool/Component Accessibility:

The Ledger Infrastructure's automated accessibility is facilitated through a dedicated Python library, providing a streamlined interface for blockchain interactions. The following code snippets demonstrate how this library can be used to connect to the blockchain, deploy smart contracts, and execute contract functions with ease:

```

...
print(f"Check connectivity with BESU node..")
print( get_chainid() )
...
print(f"Add test BOM..")
tx_result = add_besu(bom)
...
print(f"Check BOM hash..")
exists = get_besu( tx_result["hash"] )
...
print(f"Deprecate BOM hash..")
deprecated = deprecate_besu( tx_result["hash"] )
...

```

TR017 - Secure Communication Protocol Support:

The Ledger Infrastructure implements secure communication channels between client applications and the blockchain. The Python library employs standard Ethereum [7] libraries for transaction preparation, which inherently incorporate industry-standard cryptographic protocols for message signing and verification. These transactions are securely transmitted to the Hyperledger Besu blockchain using HTTPS/TLS protocols, ensuring end-to-end encryption of all communications.

TR018 - Machine-Readable Data Input/Output:

The Ledger Infrastructure component satisfies TR018 through its Python library implementation. This library inherently handles data input and output using standardized formats, ensuring seamless integration with other systems and components. For comprehensive details on the supported data structures and formats, users can refer to the fully documented README file in the Ledger Infrastructure repository.

Figure 21: Extract of the README.md from the Trust Storage client repository in the RESCALE GitLab repository.

TR019 - Flexible choice of Ledger/Blockchain for integration:

The Ledger Infrastructure component currently utilizes Hyperledger Besu as its underlying blockchain, that is Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) compatible. To achieve TR019, a demonstration of integration with the Ethereum blockchain is planned.

TR020 - Decoupled blockchain deployment:

The Ledger Infrastructure has successfully achieved this technical requirement through a dual approach. First, it abstracts the concept of Ledger as a registry for documents by defining an interface of standardized functionalities that the Ledger exposes to the client. Each variant provides specific realizations of these functionalities, enabling seamless switching between different solutions. This is evidenced by the TrustStorageClient (TR016, TR018) that provides endpoints and exposes a set of standardized CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) functions.

Second, the Ledger Infrastructure decouples the ledger development and deployment from the RESCALE platform. Current Ledger nodes are provided through a docker image (TR012, TR014), effectively separating them from other components. The final version of the project will further enhance this separation by operating on a remote ledger instance, ensuring complete architectural independence.

TR036 - Provide blockchain underlying infrastructure:

The requirement has been comprehensively covered in Chapter 3 of deliverable D4.4 - TBOM Security and Trust Mechanism, which details the process that led to the selection of Hyperledger BESU as the blockchain of reference for the RESCALE project. Figure 22 reports the chapter structure as reference.

3	Ledger Infrastructure for the Trusted Bill of Materials	17
3.1	Selection Criteria for the Ledger Platform	17
3.1.1	Justification for Using Blockchain as a Ledger	17
3.1.2	Key Criteria for Selecting the Blockchain Platform	18
3.2	Overview of blockchain platforms	20
3.2.1	BESU as the Preferred Ledger for RESCALE	21
3.2.2	Consensus Mechanism, Security, and Governance in BESU	23
3.3	The Role of the InterPlanetary File System in the Trust Storage Architecture	26
3.3.1	Introduction to IPFS	26
3.3.2	Integration of IPFS in the Trust Storage System	28

Figure 22: Chapter 3 structure from D4.4 - TBOM Security and Trust Mechanism

TR037 - Provide a homogeneous metrics for blockchain comparison:

The requirement has been successfully addressed, as demonstrated in the context of TR036. Specifically, section 3.1.2 "Key Criteria for Selecting the Blockchain Platform" in Chapter 3 of deliverable D4.4 presents a comprehensive analysis of metrics for comparing blockchain platforms. Figure 23 provides a screenshot of the final metrics table used in the comparison.

Parameter	Explanation	Importance	Quantification
Type	Distinguishes between public, permissioned, and private blockchains	Determines decentralization level	Public, Permissioned, Private
Consensus Mechanism	Describes how network participants reach agreement on transactions	Affects security, speed, and energy efficiency	Type of consensus mechanism
Scalability (TPS)	Measures transaction throughput	High throughput is critical	Numeric value representing TPS
Security	Assesses resilience to attacks and vulnerabilities	Ensures data integrity and trustworthiness	Qualitative assessment
Interoperability	Ability to integrate with other blockchains and external systems	Enhances integration flexibility	Qualitative assessment
Governance	Framework for decision-making on protocol updates	Affects adaptability	On-chain or off-chain
Cost (Tx Fees)	Transaction costs required for conducting transactions	Impacts affordability	Numeric value in USD
Developer Ecosystem	Size and activity of the developer community	Resource availability for development	Qualitative assessment
Privacy	Level of data confidentiality and privacy	Important for data protection	Qualitative assessment
Compliance	Ability to meet regulatory and legal requirements	Critical for regulated industries	Qualitative assessment

Figure 23: Metrics described in Section 3.1.2 of D4.4 - TBOM Security and Trust Mechanism

TR038 - Provide smart contracts deployment strategy:

The requirement has been achieved with the deployment of a smart contract that effectively support supply chain operations within RESCALE. This contract manages TBOMs through key operations: Add, Read, and Deprecate. Figure 24 provides reference of the code.

```

1  pragma solidity ^0.8.0;
2
3  contract HashManager {
4
5      struct HashInfo {
6          uint256 index;
7          address owner;
8      }
9
10     mapping(bytes32 => HashInfo) private hashMapping;
11     bytes32[] private hashList;
12
13     event HashAdded(bytes32 indexed hashValue, address indexed owner);
14     event HashUpdated(bytes32 indexed oldHashValue, bytes32 indexed newHashValue, address indexed owner);
15     event HashDeprecated(bytes32 indexed hashValue, address indexed owner);
16
17     function add(bytes32 _hash) external {
18         require(_hash != bytes32(0), "Invalid hash");
19         require(hashMapping[_hash].owner == address(0), "Hash already exists");
20         hashMapping[_hash] = HashInfo({ index: hashList.length, owner: msg.sender });
21         hashList.push(_hash);
22         emit HashAdded(_hash, msg.sender);
23     }
24
25     function read(bytes32 _hash) external view returns (uint256 index, address owner) {
26         require(hashMapping[_hash].owner != address(0), "Hash does not exist");
27         HashInfo memory hashInfo = hashMapping[_hash];
28         return (hashInfo.index, hashInfo.owner);
29     }
30
31     function deprecate(bytes32 _hash) external {
32         require(hashMapping[_hash].owner != address(0), "Hash does not exist");
33         require(hashMapping[_hash].owner == msg.sender, "Caller is not the owner");
34         uint256 index = hashMapping[_hash].index;
35         uint256 lastIndex = hashList.length - 1;
36         if (index != lastIndex) {
37             bytes32 lastHash = hashList[lastIndex];
38             hashList[index] = lastHash;
39             hashMapping[lastHash].index = index;
40         }
41         hashList.pop();
42         delete hashMapping[_hash];
43         emit HashDeprecated(_hash, msg.sender);
44     }
45 }
46

```

Figure 24: HashManager source code

TR039 - Smart contract data structure:

The smart contract mentioned in TR038 implements an efficient data structure for storing TBOM information. The contract stores hashes of TBOMs rather than full TBOM data. This approach minimizes blockchain operation costs by reducing data size while maintaining the minimum amount of information required to prove integrity. The smart contract utilizes two main data structures: a hashmap linking TBOM hashes to owner account addresses and a list of hashes that keeps references to the hashes stored in the hashmap.

```

10     mapping(bytes32 => HashInfo) private hashMapping;
11     bytes32[] private hashList;

```

Figure 25: Data structures in HashManager

TR040 - Implement strategies for bugs-free deployment of smart contracts:

To achieve the requirement, a set of strategies will be implemented:

- thorough code reviews by experienced team members;
- comprehensive testing, including unit tests and integration tests;

- adherence to secure coding practices, such as input validation and proper error handling;
- implementation of access control measures using modifiers
- conduct a basic security audit using automated tools.

TR041 - TBOM Life cycle management:

The TBOM lifecycle management was comprehensively described in deliverable D4.1 – Specification of the TBOM Structures. Building upon this specification, the implementation phase has focused on developing the necessary infrastructure to support these lifecycle requirements. As already documented in previous requirements (TR038, TR039), the Ledger Infrastructure provides the required tools under the form of smart contract methods to manage core states (Add, Read, Deprecate) of the TBOM life cycle. To fully support all the supply chain requirements of the RESCALE project, the smart contract will be enhanced with additional methods and data structures:

- enhanced management of TBOM ownership with hierarchical accounts functionality;
- support for additional metadata bound to TBOM entries.

3.4.3 KPI Indicators

Table 9: List of KPIs related to the Ledger Infrastructure Component

KPI	Title	Tool	Validation method	Status
KPI3.1	Write at least 3 software and hardware TBOM entries in the RESCALE public blockchain	Ledger Infrastructure	Demonstration	In progress
KPI3.3	Update and validate at least 3 software and hardware TBOM enabled applications	Ledger Infrastructure	Demonstration	In progress

KPI3.1 - Write at least 3 software and hardware TBOM entries in the RESCALE public blockchain:

This KPI will be achieved during the following phases of the project. All the necessary technologies are in place and only necessitate that all other components of RESCALE be composed and run for the demonstration. The Ledger Infrastructure has demonstrated its readiness to fulfill this KPI through several technical requirements that have already been achieved:

- TR012 confirms that the Ledger Infrastructure can be easily downloaded and run using Docker commands, providing the foundation for blockchain operations

- TR014 validates the Docker compatibility of the Ledger Infrastructure, specifically utilizing a dockerized image of Hyperledger BESU
- TR016 demonstrates the automated accessibility through a dedicated Python library that provides a streamlined interface for blockchain interactions
- TR038 shows the successful deployment of smart contracts with key operations (Add, Read, Deprecate) that will be used to write TBOM entries to the blockchain
- TR041 confirms that the Ledger Infrastructure provides the required tools to manage core states of the TBOM life cycle

KPI3.3 - Update and validate at least 3 software and hardware TBOM enabled applications:

This KPI will also be achieved during the following phases of the project. The technical foundation is completely established and only requires the integration of all RESCALE components for the demonstration. The readiness of the Ledger Infrastructure to support this KPI is evidenced by:

- TR012 and TR014 which ensure the Ledger Infrastructure’s availability and compatibility with Docker environments
- TR016 which provides the Python library interface needed for applications to interact with the blockchain
- TR018 which ensures machine-readable data input/output through standardized formats, facilitating seamless integration with other systems and components
- TR038 which implements the smart contract functionality necessary for updating and validating TBOM entries
- TR041 which provides the tools to manage the TBOM lifecycle, including updates and validation operations

3.5 Security Assurance Module

The Continuous Security Assurance Mechanism operates on a Security and Privacy Assurance Platform that dynamically evaluates the relevance and accuracy of Trust-Based Object Models (TBOMs) for hardware and software components in the face of emerging vulnerabilities and faults. Whenever new security issues arise that were not accounted for during the initial creation of a TBOM, the platform activates a targeted update process, ensuring that the supply chain remains secure and resilient over time.

3.5.1 Technical Requirements

Table 10: List of Initial Functional and Non-Functional Requirements related to the Continuous Security Assurance component

TRID	Requirement Title	Component	Validation Method	Status
TR051	New Static/dynamic report	Continuous Security Assurance	Integration testing	Achieved
TR052	Periodic assessment	Continuous Security Assurance	Integration testing	Achieved
TR053	Response Time	Continuous Security Assurance	Integration testing	Achieved
TR054	High Availability	Continuous Security Assurance	Demonstration	Achieved
TR055	Interoperability	Continuous Security Assurance	Integration testing and Demonstration	Achieved

3.5.2 Evaluation Results

TR051 - New Static/dynamic report

The system assesses at run time if the TBOM reports about a software or hardware components remains valid against currently known vulnerabilities. The system must be able to ingest the results of the static and dynamic analyzer, get the identified vulnerabilities from the National Vulnerability Database and based on the CPE of the assets (software or hardware), find the vulnerabilities that can apply.

TR052 - Periodic assessment

The security assurance system assesses at specific intervals (e.g., daily), if the valid TBOMs remain valid against currently known vulnerabilities retrieved from the National Vulnerability Database. Based on the CPE of the assets (software or hardware), the system should identify applicable vulnerabilities.

TR053 - Response Time

The security assurance system provides responses to actions/assessments within seconds under normal operation conditions. This can be measured analyzing the time that the provided services take to reply to the requests.

Method	URL	Status	Response Time
POST	https://rescale.sphynxlabs.net/auth/realms/assurance/protocol/openid-connect/token	200	369 ms
POST	https://rescale.sphynxlabs.net/auth/realms/assurance/protocol/openid-connect/token	200	145 ms
POST	https://rescale.sphynxlabs.net/auth/realms/assurance/protocol/openid-connect/token	200	177 ms
POST	https://rescale.sphynxlabs.net/auth/realms/assurance/protocol/openid-connect/token	200	196 ms

Figure 26: Response Time

TR054 - High Availability

The security assurance system will be available 99.5% of the time, excluding planned maintenance windows. The security assurance platform itself has been implemented in such a way to provide 24/7 functionality, the cloud instances availability will be directly related to the SLA given by the cloud providers, which is higher than 99.5%.

TR055 - Interoperability

The security assurance system exchanges data with other components and tools via well-defined APIs, supporting formats such as JSON and XML. The following is an example of one API used in STS that specify JSON as response type, with the use of the "produces = MediaType.APPLICATION_JSON_VALUE".

```

...
@PostMapping(
    path = "/organisations/{organisationId}/projects/{projectId}/owners/{ownerId}",
    consumes = MediaType.MULTIPART_FORM_DATA_VALUE,
    produces = MediaType.APPLICATION_JSON_VALUE)
public ResponseEntity<SuccessMessage> importSBOM(
    @PathVariable @Positive Long projectId,
    @PathVariable @Positive Long organisationId,
    @PathVariable UUID ownerId,
    @RequestParam("sbomFormat") @Valid SBOMFormatEnum sbomFormat,
    @RequestPart("file") MultipartFile file) {
...

```

3.5.3 KPI Indicators

Table 11: List of KPI Indicators related to the Continuous Security Assurance component

TRID	Requirement Title	Component	Validation Method	Status
KPI2.1	Highly accurate vulnerability assessment algorithms more than 98% for known benchmark applications	Continuous Security Assurance	Demonstration	In progress

KPI2.2	Detect more than 90% of known vulnerabilities at hardware and software level for the pilot's vulnerable hardware and software solutions	Continuous Security Assurance	Demonstration	In progress
KPI4.3	Detection of more than 95% of total insecure components during piloting activities for known benchmark applications	Continuous Security Assurance	Demonstration	In progress

KPI2.1 – Highly accurate vulnerability assessment algorithms (98%) for known benchmark applications

This KPI will be addressed through the execution of standard benchmarking tests in the near future. The objective is to validate the accuracy and reliability of the vulnerability assessment algorithms by applying them to recognized benchmark applications and verifying that they meet or exceed the 98% accuracy threshold. To evaluate its performance, a set of benchmark TBOMs will be utilized, where vulnerabilities are manually or synthetically inserted and validated by security experts. The module will be executed on these TBOMs, and its results will be cross-referenced with the established ground truth.

KPI2.2 – Detection of more than 90% of known vulnerabilities at the hardware and software level for the pilot's vulnerable hardware and software solutions

This KPI will be achieved at the end of the piloting activities. The necessary technologies supporting the Continuous Security Assurance component have already been developed and are fully operational. Final integration with the rest of the RESCALE architecture is needed to enable the full system to perform end-to-end vulnerability detection.

KPI4.3 – Detection of more than 95% of total insecure components during piloting activities for known benchmark applications

This KPI will be achieved at the end of the piloting activities. The Continuous Security Assurance infrastructure is in place and technically capable of identifying insecure components with high accuracy. Final integration with the rest of the RESCALE architecture is needed to enable the full system to perform end-to-end vulnerability detection during piloting activities. To evaluate its performance, a set of insecure libraries/components will be utilized, where vulnerabilities are manually or synthetically inserted and validated by security experts. The module will be executed on the generated TBOMs, and its results will be cross-referenced with the established ground truth.

3.6 State Manager Module

The State Manager acts as the central orchestrator for the RESCALE platform's backend, handling API requests from all components outside the management layer, providing API endpoints for the rest of the RESCALE components to enable their functionalities, such as the Dashboard, the Static Code Analysis Module, Dynamic Testing Module, the TrustOR, and the Security Assurance pipeline, allowing for inter-connectivity, and enabling the data flow inside the RESCALE platform.

3.6.1 Technical Requirements

TRID	Requirement Title	Component	Validation Method	Status
TR007	Generate SSCG	State Manager	Integration testing with Static Analysis Module	Achieved
TR011	Generate DSCG	State Manager	Integration testing with Dynamic Analysis Module	In progress
TR012	Tools/components should be able to "download and run"	State Manager	Deployment and accessibility tests	Achieved
TR013	Documentation Completeness	State Manager	README.md and OpenAPI	In progress
TR014	OpenAPI-compliant API Documentation	State Manager	OpenAPI validation via Swagger	In progress
TR018	Machine-readable Data Input/Output	State Manager	Demonstration	Achieved
TR021	RESCALE Common Storage Repository	State Manager	Demonstration	Achieved
TR056	User role-based access control, Authentication	State Manager	Demonstration	Achieved
TR057	User Notifications	State Manager	Demonstration	Scheduled for M21

3.6.2 Evaluation Results

TR007 - Generate SSCG: The State Manager receives the SSCG report from the Static Analysis Module, extracts information such as the Serial Number and the version, associates it with the corresponding component and forwards it to TrustOR for persistent storing as shown in Figure 27. The Dashboard retrieves the SSCG for visualization through the State Manager.

```

Requested URL: /sscgc
Access Token Validated
INFO 172.18.0.5:53190 - "POST /api/sbom_sscgc/ HTTP/1.1" 200
Component updated with new version: 2.6.2
Component updated with SSCGC: bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3134f9cd1073
Component updated successfully: {
  details: {
    Title: 'Component1',
    ProgrammingLanguage: 'Programming Language of Component 1',
    Description: 'Description of Component 1'
  },
  _id: new ObjectId('67eba258d077f781ae4236ab'),
  userId: '666',
  hash: 'hash1',
  versions: [
    {
      version: '2.6.2',
      statusSSCG: 'bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3134f9cd1073',
      statusDSCG: 'UNAVAILABLE',
      statusTBOM: 'UNAVAILABLE',
      validateTBOM: false,
      _id: new ObjectId('67eba27ed077f781ae4236b5')
    }
  ]
},

```

Figure 27: State Manager SSCGC Generation process

TR011 - Generate DSCG: The State Manager receives the DSCG report from the Dynamic Analysis Module, extracts information such as the Serial Number, associates it with the corresponding component and SSCGC report and forwards it to TrustOR for persistent storing as shown in Figure 28.

```

Requested URL: /dscgc
Access Token Validated
INFO 172.18.0.5:35380 - "POST /api/dscgc/ HTTP/1.1" 200
INFO STEP-1: TBOM creation started
INFO STEP-1: adding SBOM, SSCGC & DSCGC components
{"t":{"$date":"2025-04-01T08:25:24.457+00:00"},"s":"I","c":"STORAGE","id":20320,"ctx":"conn3","msg":"createCollection","attr":{"namespace":"rescale.bov_collection":"generated"},"uid":{"$uid":"88c51670-e372-4030-ad29-c858056342bd"},"options":{}}
INFO STEP-1: BOV creation & validation: PASSED
Component updated successfully: {
  details: {
    Title: 'Component1',
    ProgrammingLanguage: 'Programming Language of Component 1',
    Description: 'Description of Component 1'
  },
  _id: new ObjectId('67eba2e9d9dca3c774b0d377'),
  userId: '666',
  hash: 'hash1',
  versions: [
    {
      version: '2.6.2',
      statusSSCG: 'bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3134f9cd1073',
      statusDSCG: '3e671687-391b-41f5-a30f-a58921a69b78',
      statusTBOM: '25dfc0b6-13aa-48a2-b1fe-f06a8baf1f92',
      validateTBOM: false,
      _id: new ObjectId('67eba2f0d9dca3c774b0d381')
    }
  ]
},

```

Figure 28: State Manager SSCGC Generation process

TR012 - Tools/components should be able to "download and run": State Manager is avail-

able for download via harbor as docker image as depicted in Figure 29.

```
sceptum@192 dev-platform % docker pull harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/state_manager:latest
latest: Pulling from rescale-all/state_manager
Digest: sha256:a5ddb34813469b95c51595bff95d99aba7e61d562ebf92ad0c5188dc2e432148
Status: Image is up to date for harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/state_manager:latest
harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/state_manager:latest
sceptum@192 dev-platform % docker pull harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/dashboard:latest
latest: Pulling from rescale-all/dashboard
Digest: sha256:9c06987bf302245f02a2c5da7e363d9b47ced773d66b97d876abe743e296a98d
Status: Image is up to date for harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/dashboard:latest
harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/dashboard:latest
```

Figure 29: State Manager docker pull from harbor

Afterwards, it can be run with the docker compose command as shown in Figure 30

```
sceptum@192 dev-platform % docker compose up state-manager
[*] Running 3/0
  ✓ Container mongodb      Running      0.0s
  ✓ Container trustor      Running      0.0s
  ✓ Container state-manager Created      0.0s
Attaching to state-manager
state-manager | connectDB
state-manager | Websocket Server Initialized
state-manager | (node:1) [MONGODB DRIVER] Warning: useNewUrlParser is a deprecated option: useNewUrlParser has no effect since Node.js Driver version 4.0.0 and will be removed in the
next major version
state-manager | (Use 'node --trace-warnings ...' to show where the warning was created)
state-manager | (node:1) [MONGODB DRIVER] Warning: useUnifiedTopology is a deprecated option: useUnifiedTopology has no effect since Node.js Driver version 4.0.0 and will be removed in
the next major version
state-manager | Server running at http://localhost:3000/
state-manager | Connected to MongoDB successfully.
```

Figure 30: State Manager running as docker image

TR013 - Documentation Completeness: Documentation for the State Manager component, about its configurations and deployment details, can be found at the README.md under RESCALE's [State Manager GitLab repository](#).

TR014 - OpenAPI-compliant API Documentation: The State Manager provides an OpenAPI-compliant API documentation. It is implemented using Node.js with the Express framework and leverages Swagger to generate an interactive endpoint documentation as shown in Figure 31.

The screenshot displays the OpenAPI documentation for the State Manager module. At the top, it shows the title 'State Manager' with version indicators '1.0.0' and 'OAS 3.0'. Below the title, it states 'API documentation for the State Manager Module'. A 'Servers' dropdown menu is set to 'http://localhost:3000'. The main content is a list of endpoints under the 'default' environment. Each endpoint is represented by a colored bar indicating its method: GET (blue), DELETE (red), and POST (green). The endpoints and their descriptions are as follows:

Method	Endpoint	Description
GET	/dashboard/getAllUsers	Retrieve all users
GET	/dashboard/getUserInfo/{userId}	Retrieve user information
GET	/dashboard/getAllComponents/	Retrieve all components
GET	/dashboard/getAllUserComponents/{userId}	Retrieve all components of a specific user
DELETE	/dashboard/flushComponents	Flush all components
DELETE	/dashboard/flushComponent/{userId}/{componentName}	Flush a specific component of a user
POST	/repo/component	Set asset
GET	/repo/asset/{userId}/{componentId}	Retrieve asset
GET	/sscGet/{id}	Retrieve SSCG data by Component Hash
GET	/sbomGet/{id}	Retrieve SBOM (Software Bill of Materials) data by ID
POST	/ssc	Receive SSCG and SBOM from SSCG Generator and store in repo
GET	/repo/dscg	Retrieve DSCG from repo
POST	/dscg	Retrieve DSCG from DSCG Generator
POST	/tbom	Receive TBOM generation notification + TBOM UUID
POST	/securityAssurance	Forward security assurance notification to the dashboard

Figure 31: State Manager OpenAPI Documentation

TR018 - Machine-readable Data Input/Output:

State Manager handles API requests and responses using structured, machine-readable formats. Specifically, it follows the JSON and Cyclone DX format, ensuring seamless integration with other components within the RESCALE ecosystem. The API endpoints, documented via Swagger, define the expected input/output structures, enabling automated processing and interoperability with external tools. Figure 32 shows an example of such a procedure, using POSTMAN to send API requests in a machine-readable input/output. On the upper part, the request is shown, structured in JSON format, and on the lower part the response, following a JSON format.

Figure 32: Machine Readable I/O

TR021 - RESCALE Common Storage Repository: State Manager uses a internal database implemented in MongoDB, to store information about RESCALE Users and their associated components. Figure 33 showcases the MongoDB collections used by State Manager.

Viewing Database: admin

Collections				Collection Name	+ Create collection
View	Export	[JSON]	Import	components	Del
View	Export	[JSON]	Import	system.users	Del
View	Export	[JSON]	Import	system.version	Del
View	Export	[JSON]	Import	users	Del
View	Export	[JSON]	Import	vulns	Del

Figure 33: MongoDB Collections utilised by State Manager

TR056 - User role-based access control, Authentication: This requirement is fulfilled through the integration of Keycloak, which provides robust authentication and role-based access con-

trol. Users are authenticated via OpenID Connect, and their access to platform functionalities is restricted based on roles defined and managed within the Keycloak realm as shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34: State Manager shown as a Keycloak client inside a Keycloak Realm

TR057 - User Notifications: The implementation of TR057 has not yet started. Consequently, at this stage, no evaluation activities have been conducted, and evidence for its validation is not available. The progress on this requirement will be reported in future updates once implementation begins.

3.6.3 KPI Indicators

KPI	Title	Component	Validation Method	Status
KPI 4.4	Construction of an informative mechanism for both security and non-security experts	State Manager	Demonstration	In progress

This KPI evaluates the platform’s ability to deliver security-related information in a way that is meaningful, accessible, and actionable for both technical (e.g., security experts) and non-technical (e.g., business users or managers) stakeholders. The following assessment focuses on the roles played by the **State Manager** in supporting this objective.

Its design ensures:

- **Clarity of information:** Output reports such as SSCG, SBOM, DSCG, TBOM are available for retrieval and display via HTTP RestFUL API endpoints(JSON reponses/re-quests) enabling integration with user-facing tools.
- **Actionability:** The State Manager enables downstream actions by:
 - Providing secure access tokens for SSCG and DSCG generators to submit analysis results, enabling automated workflows.
 - Forwarding reports to TrustOR, which is responsible for consolidating SBOM, SSCG, and DSCG into a Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM).
 - Enabling TBOM validation by forwarding the TBOM hash to TrustOR, which handles verification via the blockchain module.
 - Allowing retrieval of individual or versioned security artifacts.
 - Supporting vulnerability update propagation via periodic communication with the TrustOR and Security Assurance module. When new vulnerabilities are detected and associated with a TBOM, the State Manager updates the corresponding records and exposes them through the RESCALE Dashboard.

3.7 Dashboard

The Rescale Dashboard provides a user-friendly interface that streamlines access to testing functionalities and consolidates all relevant information in a structured manner. By offering intuitive navigation and real-time insights, the dashboard enhances the assessment process, allowing users to evaluate software and hardware components efficiently and make informed decisions.

3.7.1 Technical Requirements

TR ID	Title	Component	Validation Method	Status
TR006	Show the results of static analysis	Dashboard	Demonstration	Achieved
TR007	Generate SSCG	Dashboard	Integration testing with Static Analysis Module	Achieved
TR010	Show the results of dynamic analysis	Dashboard	Demonstration	Achieved
TR011	Generate DSCG	Dashboard	Integration testing with Dynamic Analysis Module	In progress

TR012	Tools/components should be able to "download and run"	Dashboard	Deployment and accessibility tests	Achieved
TR056	User role-based access control, Authentication	Dashboard	Demonstration	Achieved
TR057	User Notifications	Dashboard	Demonstration	Scheduled for M21

3.7.2 Evaluation Results

TR006 - Show the results of static analysis :

Upon completing the static analysis, the dashboard updates to reflect the new status of the SSCG. It then provides the user with the option to inspect the JSON of the SSCG as shown in the Figure 35.

```

SSCG Inspector

bomFormat: "CycloneDX"
specVersion: "1.6"
serialNumber: "urn:uuid:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3164f9cd1093"
version: 1
▼ metadata:
  ▼ authors:
    timestamp: "2024-12-06T13:00:48Z"
  ▼ tools:
    ▼ components:
      ▼ 0:
        ▼ data:
          ▼ 0:
            ▼ contents:
              ▼ attachment:
                content: "--sbom /home/mate/repo/grisp/sbom.json --test
                /home/mate/repo/sscg_generator/priv/input/tests --output
                ./sscg.json --authors "
                name: "CLI configuration flags"
                type: "configuration"
                description: "A ReSCALE certified tool to generate SSCGs"
            ▼ hashes:
              ▼ 0:
                alg: "SHA-1"
                content: "2fd4e1c67a2d28fced849ee1bb76e7391b93eb12"
                name: "ReSCALE SSCG Generator"
                purl: "pkg:hex/sscg_generator@0.1.0"
                type: "application"
                version: "0.1.0"
          ▼ 1:
            ▼ data:
              ▼ 0:
                ▼ contents:
                  ▼ attachment:
                    content: "RESCALE_STATIC_ANALYSIS_LANG=erlang
                    RESCALE_DRY_RUN=false"
                    name: "Docker Environment"
                    type: "configuration"
                    description: "A ReSCALE certified container to execute static testing"
                ▼ hashes:
                  ▼ 0:
                    alg: "SHA-1"
                    content: "35d1c8f259129dc800ec8e073bb68f995424619c"
                    name: "ReSCALE Static Code Analysis Module"
                    purl: "pkg:docker/static_code_analysis_module@1.0.0"
                    type: "container"
                    version: "1.0.0"

```

Figure 35: SSCG Inspection

TR007 - Generate SSCG:

Once a Producer registers a component, the option to initiate the generation of a static analysis report becomes available. Through the dashboard as seen in Figure 36, the Producer can access and copy the required access token to proceed with the static analysis process.

Figure 36: Getting the Access Token from the Dashboard to initiate SSCG generation

TR010 - Show the results of dynamic analysis:

Once the dynamic analysis is completed and the DSCG becomes available, the dashboard updates its contents accordingly, providing the user with the option to inspect the generated DSCG report as it is demonstrated in the Figure 37.

```


DSCG Inspector


bomFormat: "CycloneDX"
specVersion: "1.6"
serialNumber: "urn:uuid:3e671687-391b-41f5-a30f-a58921a69b78"
version: 1
  metadata:
    timestamp: "2024-09-03T05:48:47.302Z"
    authors:
      0:
        name: "Some Company/person that wants to generate a DSCG for their binary"
        email: "some@company.com"
    tools:
      components:
        0:
          type: "application"
          name: "ReSCALE DSCG Generator"
          version: "1.4.17"
          description: "A ReSCALE certified tool to generate DSCGs"
          purl: "pkg:hex/dscg-generator@1.4.17"
          data:
            0:
              name: "CLI configuration flags"
              type: "configuration"
              contents:
                attachment:
                  content: "--test-report=report.json --output=dscg.json"
          hashes:
            0:
              alg: "SHA-1"
              content: "3942447fac867ae5cdb3229b658f4d48"
        1:
          type: "container"
          name: "ReSCALE dynamic Code Analysis Module"
          version: "2.1.7"
          description: "A ReSCALE certified container to execute dynamic testing"
          purl: "pkg:docker/dynamic-code-analysis-module@2.1.7"
          data:
            0:
              name: "Docker Environment"
              type: "configuration"
              contents:
                attachment:
                  content: "RESCALE_DYNAMIC_ANALYSIS_LANG=erlang
RESCALE_DRY_RUN=false"
          hashes:
```

Figure 37: DSCG Inspection

TR011 - Generate DSCG:

Once the Producer has generated a version of the SSCG for a specific component and a serial number has been assigned, the Consumer can use the provided access token along with the serial number from the appropriate fields of the dashboard as shown in the Figure 38, to initiate the necessary procedures for generating the dynamic analysis report.

Figure 38: Getting the Access Token and the Serial Number from the Dashboard

TR012 - Tools/components should be able to "download and run": The Dashboard component is available for download via harbor as docker image as depicted in Figure 39.

```
sceptum@192 dev-platform % docker pull harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/state_manager:latest
latest: Pulling from rescale-all/state_manager
Digest: sha256:a5ddb34813469b95c51595bff95d99aba7e61d562ebf92ad0c5188dc2e432148
Status: Image is up to date for harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/state_manager:latest
harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/state_manager:latest
sceptum@192 dev-platform % docker pull harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/dashboard:latest
latest: Pulling from rescale-all/dashboard
Digest: sha256:9c06987bf302245f02a2c5da7e363d9b47ced773d66b97d876abe743e296a98d
Status: Image is up to date for harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/dashboard:latest
harbor.rescale-project.eu/rescale-all/dashboard:latest
```

Figure 39: Dashboard Docker pull from harbor

Afterwards, it can be run with the docker compose command as shown in Figure 40

```
sceptum@192 dev-platform % docker compose up avt
[+] Running 4/0
 ✓ Container mongodb      Running      0.0s
 ✓ Container trustor      Running      0.0s
 ✓ Container state-manager Running      0.0s
 ✓ Container dashboard    Created      0.0s
Attaching to dashboard
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [warn] 1#1: could not build optimal proxy_headers_hash, you should increase either proxy_headers_hash_max_size: 512 or proxy_headers_hash_bucket_size: 64; ignoring proxy_headers_hash_bucket_size
dashboard | nginx: [warn] could not build optimal proxy_headers_hash, you should increase either proxy_headers_hash_max_size: 512 or proxy_headers_hash_bucket_size: 64; ignoring proxy_headers_hash_bucket_size
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: using the "epoll" event method
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: nginx/1.27.4
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: built by gcc 14.2.0 (Alpine 14.2.0)
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: OS: Linux 6.10.11-linuxkit
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: getrlimit(RLIMIT_NOFILE): 1048576:1048576
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker processes
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker process 8
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker process 9
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker process 10
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker process 11
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker process 12
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker process 13
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker process 14
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker process 15
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker process 16
dashboard | 2025/03/14 11:20:14 [notice] 1#1: start worker process 17
```

Figure 40: Dashboard running as Docker image

TR056 - User role-based access control, Authentication:

Figure 41 demonstrates the interface and functionalities available to the Producer role. Producers have the ability to register a component, view their registered components, access the

SSCG, and generate a static analysis report. The role-based access control mechanism ensures that only producers can perform these actions, restricting access to functionalities intended for consumers.

Figure 41: Producer's View

Figure 42 illustrates the interface and functionalities available to the Consumer role. Consumers have an overview of all registered components, allowing them to perform dynamic analysis on the available components. Additionally, they can inspect the JSON output of the static analysis if it is available, but they do not have the rights to perform the static analysis themselves.

Figure 42: Consumer's View

TR057 - User Notifications:

The implementation of TR057 has not yet started. Consequently, at this stage, no evaluation activities have been conducted, and evidence for its validation is not available. The progress on this requirement will be reported in future updates once implementation begins.

3.7.3 KPI Indicators

KPI	Title	Component	Validation Method	Status
KPI 4.4	Construction of an informative mechanism for both security and non-security experts	Dashboard	Demonstration	In progress

The Dashboard serves as the main interface for platform users, offering tailored views based on user roles (e.g., producer or consumer). It is designed to support both interaction and visualization of assessment workflows and security information. It provides differentiated views and options for different user roles. It displays vulnerabilities by severity levels, aiding prioritization and quick risk assessment. Additionally, it includes filters, search, and component version tracking to facilitate navigation.

4 System-Level Validation

System-level validation ensures that the integrated components function correctly as a cohesive unit, meeting overall system requirements and performance expectations. It assesses the interactions between components, their interoperability, and the system's ability to handle real-world scenarios. This process involves comprehensive testing techniques, including integration testing, end-to-end validation, stress testing, and scenario-based simulations, to verify that the system operates reliably under various conditions. By identifying inconsistencies, bottlenecks, and potential failures at this stage, system-level validation plays a crucial role in guaranteeing the robustness and effectiveness of the final product.

In this phase of the project, a system-level validation will be conducted on the integrated MVP solution. This upcoming validation phase will confirm that all components work together seamlessly in real-world scenarios, fulfilling the project's functional and non-functional requirements.

4.1 Technical Requirements

Table 16 presents the traceability matrix of the initial functional and non-functional requirements. This matrix serves as a structured overview linking each identified requirement to its corresponding system components. It ensures that all functional and non-functional aspects are accounted for and properly addressed throughout the development process, providing clear visibility and traceability from the early stages of requirements definition to implementation. The matrix provides an overview of the requirements' implementation status, categorized as Scheduled (not yet started but there is plan), In Progress (partially implemented), and Yes (fully implemented). Also, the presented traceability matrix illustrates which system components need to collaborate in order to fulfill each specific functional or non-functional requirement. The matrix highlights dependencies and integration points necessary for successful implementation and validation.

Table 16: Traceability Matrix of Initial Functional and Non-Functional Requirements

Req. ID	Software Static Code Analysis Module	Dynamic Testing Module	TrustOR	Ledger Infrastructure	Security Assurance Module	State Manager Module + Dashboard
TR001			Yes			
TR002			Yes			
TR003	Yes					
TR004	In progress					
TR005	In progress					
TR006	In progress					Yes
TR007	In progress					Yes
TR008		In progress				
TR009		Yes				

Table 16 – continued from previous page

Req. ID	Software Static Code Analysis Module	Dynamic Testing Module	TrustOR	Ledger Infrastructure	Security Assurance Module	State Manager Module
TR010		Yes				Yes
TR011		Yes				In progress
TR012	In progress	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes
TR013	In progress	In progress	In progress	Yes		In progress
TR014	In progress	Yes	Yes	Yes		In progress
TR015			Yes			
TR016	In progress	In progress		Yes		
TR017	Scheduled	In progress	Yes	Yes		
TR018	In progress	In progress	Yes	Yes		Yes
TR019				Yes		
TR020				Yes		
TR021			Yes			Yes
TR022	Scheduled	Yes				
TR023	Scheduled					
TR024	In progress					
TR025	In progress					
TR026	Scheduled					
TR027	In progress					
TR028	Scheduled					
TR029	Yes					
TR030	Yes					
TR031		In progress				
TR032		In progress				
TR033		In progress				
TR034		In progress				
TR035		In progress				
TR036				Yes		
TR037				Yes		
TR038				Yes		
TR039				Yes		
TR040				In progress		
TR041			In progress	In progress		
TR042			Yes			
TR043			Yes			
TR044			In progress			
TR045			In progress			
TR046			In progress			
TR047		In progress				
TR048		Yes				
TR049		Yes				
TR050		Yes				
TR051					Yes	

Table 16 – continued from previous page

Req. ID	Software Static Code Analysis Module	Dynamic Testing Module	TrustOR	Ledger Infrastructure	Security Assurance Module	State Manager Module
TR052					Yes	
TR053					Yes	
TR054					Yes	
TR055					Yes	
TR056						Yes
TR057						Scheduled

4.2 Impact KPI Indicators

The table below presents a traceability matrix that links each Impact Key Performance Indicator (iKPI) to the evaluation method and RESCALE module/tool responsible for its validation. This approach ensures that all impact measurements are systematically aligned with the project's core technologies and validation mechanisms. The traceability matrix provides:

- A structured overview of impact KPIs, defining their scope and objectives.
- Validation methods used to assess their effectiveness, such as benchmark testing, stakeholder feedback, and compliance mapping.
- Mapping to RESCALE tools, ensuring that each iKPI is supported by the appropriate module for measurement and verification.

By incorporating this structured approach, the RESCALE project can demonstrate the effectiveness of its technical solutions and the broader impact on supply chain security, regulatory frameworks, and industry adoption.

4.2.1 Key Impact KPIs and Their Evaluation Framework

The following iKPIs serve as benchmarks for assessing RESCALE's impact and the modules/tools that contribute to their validation.

iKPI	Description	Validation Method	RESCALE Module/-Tool
iKPI1	Increased trust and adoption of blockchain-assisted TBOM updates by 30%	Stakeholder surveys, blockchain audit	Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR), Ledger Infrastructure

iKPI2	AI models developed for enhancing security testing accuracy (>5 models)	AI model validation, component integration reports	Static Code Analysis Module, Dynamic Testing Module
iKPI3	90% vulnerability detection coverage in secure supply chains	Pilot case assessments, benchmark testing	Static Code Analysis, Dynamic Testing Module
iKPI4	RESCALE compliance with NIS directive in 2 pilot scenarios	Regulatory compliance mapping, pilot feedback	Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR), Security Assurance Module
iKPI5	Security assessment accuracy increased by 20%	Accuracy evaluation, audit reports	Ledger Infrastructure, Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR)
iKPI6	Integration of three security modalities in assurance	Dynamic testing, runtime monitoring	Security Assurance Module, Dynamic Testing Module
iKPI7	Detection of 95% insecure mechanisms in pilot activities	Static & dynamic testing tool performance	Dynamic Testing Module
iKPI8	TBOM components' self-assessed preparedness increased by 50%	Stakeholder feedback, pilot reports	MVP Evaluation, Dashboard
iKPI9	Dynamic vulnerability assessment achieves 98% accuracy	Benchmark testing, system evaluation	Dynamic Testing Module, Security Assurance Module
iKPI10	Security auditing tools achieve 95% accuracy	Validation through security audits	Security Assurance Module, Dashboard
iKPI11	RESCALE TrustOR adoption rate exceeds 80% in pilots	Adoption tracking, user feedback	Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR), Dashboard
iKPI12	Business models proposed based on TrustOR (>2 models)	Market analysis, pilot engagement	Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR), MVP Evaluation
iKPI13	Five AI-assisted security testing models validated	AI model integration results	Security Assurance Module, AI-driven Analysis
iKPI14	Validation of RESCALE outside project scope in one cybersecurity supply chain	External pilot validation	MVP Evaluation, Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR)
iKPI15	Achieve 95% cyberattack resilience during pilots	Stress testing, security assessments	Dynamic Testing Module
iKPI16	Perception of security via TBOM and TrustOR increased by 20%	Stakeholder perception studies	Dashboard, Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR)
iKPI17	Reduce time for vulnerability detection by 10%	Detection speed benchmarking	Static Code Analysis, Dynamic Testing Module
iKPI18	At least one emerging technology trend embedded in RESCALE roadmap	Innovation tracking, technology reports	High-Level Architecture (D2.5), Technology Analysis (D2.3)

iKPI19	Impact demonstrated on three secure EU-based products/services	Exploitation assessment	MVP Evaluation, Dashboard
iKPI20	RESCALE TBOM solutions demonstrated in two supply chain domains	Adoption case studies	Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR), Ledger Infrastructure
iKPI22	More than three early adopters of the RESCALE platform	Stakeholder adoption tracking	MVP Evaluation, Dashboard
iKPI26	Security testing mechanisms achieve 95% accuracy	Validation testing, traceability analysis	Static Code Analysis, Security Assurance Module
iKPI27	80% acceptance of piloted technologies in two environments	Pilot acceptance surveys	MVP Evaluation, Dashboard

4.3 MVP Evaluation Results

This section presents end-to-end testing scenarios performed to validate the integrated components of the RESCALE ecosystem. These tests aim to verify:

- The interoperability of security assurance mechanisms,
- The detection of vulnerabilities through dynamic and static analysis,
- The usability and effectiveness of the RESCALE dashboard for tracking security metrics,
- The integration of blockchain mechanisms for supply chain transparency.

4.3.1 Test Scenario 1: Supply Chain Security Validation and TBOM Generation

Objective: Assess the security of a supply chain scenario by utilising RESCALE’s security assurance framework.

Components Integrated:

- Trust Orchestrator (TrustOR),
- Static and Dynamic Testing Modules,
- RESCALE Dashboard,
- State Manager,
- Security Assurance Module,

- Blockchain, Infrastructure for TBOM Storage.

Test Flow:

1. **Component Registration:** The producer logs in to the Rescale Platform and registers a software or hardware component from the RESCALE dashboard as shown in Figure 43.
2. **Static Analysis Execution:** The Static Code Analysis Module runs the static analysis tools for the component under test. The results of each tool are combined into an SSCG and SBOM output, which are forwarded to the RESCALE Platform. See Figure 44.
3. **Dynamic Testing Execution:** The Dynamic Testing Module performs runtime security validation and forwards the generated DSCG output to the RESCALE Platform. See Figure 45.
4. **TBOM Creation:** When the SSCG and DSCG are generated for a component, the TrustOR initiates the TBOM generation procedure, where a TBOM entry is created and added into the blockchain.
5. **Security Assurance Monitoring:** Afterwards, the Security Assurance Module continuously monitors the TBOM's security status. See figure 46
6. **Dashboard Reporting:** All results are aggregated and displayed in the RESCALE Dashboard for end-user review.

Expected Outcome:

- Identification of all known vulnerabilities in the supply chain using RESCALE's AI-powered static and dynamic analysis.
- Secure storage of the TBOM via blockchain.
- Continuous monitoring and reporting of TBOM security statuses.

4.3.2 Test Scenario 2: TBOM Validation Workflow

Objective: Validate the process of generating and securing a TBOM within the RESCALE framework.

Components Integrated:

- State Manager
- TrustOR
- Security Assurance Module
- Blockchain Infrastructure
- RESCALE Repositories

Test Flow:

1. **Login to RESCALE Dashboard:** Authenticate using valid credentials to access the RESCALE Platform.
2. **Locate the Component associated with the TBOM under validation:** Use the search or filter options in the Dashboard to find the target component.
3. **Validate TBOM Integrity:** Use blockchain metadata shown on the Dashboard to verify that the TBOM hash matches what is stored on the blockchain.
4. **From the Component View, inspect Component's Reports for further insights about the vulnerabilities detected:** These include vulnerability reports included in the SSCG, SBOM, DSCG, and updates from the Bill of Vulnerabilities through continuous monitoring.

Expected Outcome:

- Successful response from Rescale Platform if TBOM is found in the blockchain.
- Continuous monitoring for validation of software and hardware components.
- Automated compliance checks within the security assurance framework.

4.3.3 System Integration Sequence Diagram

A sequence diagram is included to illustrate the full end-to-end testing flow, showcasing:

- User authentication and role-based access control (IAM) (see Figure 43),
- Component registration and security validation steps (see Figure 43),
- How static and dynamic security validation feed into TBOM generation (see Figures 44 and 45),
- Blockchain integration and verification of TBOM authenticity,
- Final security audit and dashboard reporting.

These scenarios are derived from the RESCALE High-Level Architecture (D2.5) and the established test flows. They demonstrate the seamless integration of security assurance, blockchain-based transparency, and real-time vulnerability monitoring within the RESCALE ecosystem.

Further test scenarios and additional integration validation will be described in future iterations of this document.

Figure 43: User Authentication and Component Registration

Figure 44: Static Analysis Phase

Figure 45: Dynamic Analysis Phase

Figure 46: TBOM Generation

5 User Evaluation

The user evaluation of the RESCALE platform will be conducted through a structured survey designed to assess its effectiveness, adoption potential, and impact on cybersecurity within software and hardware supply chains. By gathering feedback from key stakeholders, including security experts, developers, IT managers, and policymakers, the survey provides valuable insights into how RESCALE meets industry needs. The evaluation focuses on several aspects, such as ease of use, effectiveness in vulnerability detection, compliance with security standards, and overall adoption likelihood. In addition, the survey is designed to address key performance indicators (KPIs) relevant to the project.

This survey was developed using the EUSurvey platform and can be accessed at [5]. Additionally, the complete questionnaire is provided in the appendix of this document for further reference. Kindly note that this survey is in draft form and may undergo further revisions and enhancements at a later stage.

The collected responses will provide valuable insights into user interactions, potential areas for improvement, and the overall impact of the system in meeting its intended objectives. The results will serve as a foundation for refining the platform, enhancing its accessibility, and ensuring its alignment with real-world cybersecurity challenges.

In this stage of development, only pilot partners have completed the survey and provided feedback, including their perspective on user-friendliness, system functionality, and adoption potential.

For pilot partner CC, the RESCALE solution has proven easy to integrate with Bitbucket CI, enabling a smooth adoption within existing development workflows. The dashboard is intuitive and user-friendly, and many suggestions from the pilot have already been implemented, with further improvements in progress. The solution demonstrates significant value in strengthening security and trust in the software supply chain, and pilot partner CC plans to deploy it across a wide range of its software components.

As a pilot partner, PST's experience with the RESCALE platform has been largely positive. One of the key strengths lies in its seamless integration with existing CI environments, enabling straightforward adaptation even in brownfield scenarios. This compatibility significantly reduces friction when embedding RESCALE into legacy workflows. The intuitive dashboard further enhances user experience, providing a clean and accessible interface for monitoring and managing security workflows. While most aspects integrate well, dynamic testing remains somewhat challenging to embed due to its inherent complexity and runtime demands. Despite this, the value RESCALE brings is clear: as development continues, it offers a much clearer view of supply chains and their associated vulnerabilities. This increased transparency could make supply chain management more effective and informed.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable provides an initial evaluation and validation of the system, assessing both individual components and the integrated platform against functional and non-functional requirements and defined KPIs. We have performed a thorough mapping of requirements to system components and tools, and provided their current validation status. Furthermore, we identified the key performance indicators (KPIs) to be monitored by specific components, but at this stage, evidence of meeting these KPIs is not yet available for all of them and it will be provided in future iterations, after M18. A preliminary version of the survey for external stakeholders has been prepared, which will serve as a basis for gathering qualitative feedback on the solution's usability and effectiveness. Currently, the validation process has been limited to internal pilot partner evaluation of the MVP.

In the next phase, additional steps will be taken to strengthen the validation process, including:

- Gathering evidence and metrics to demonstrate compliance with the defined KPIs,
- Conducting comprehensive system-level validation,
- Identification and harmonization of semantically equivalent parameters across different tools within Static Code Analysis and Dynamic Testing Modules to ensure consistency in naming and interpretation,
- Rolling out the external survey and collecting feedback from stakeholders outside the consortium,
- Organizing and executing a red-blue team exercise to stress-test the solution from both offensive and defensive security perspectives.

The results of these steps will be documented in the next iteration of this deliverable, contributing to the continuous improvement of the system.

A RESCALE Evaluation Questionnaire

The full survey is provided in the following appendix. Please note that this document is currently in draft version and will be further refined and improved in the next iteration.

RESCALE Evaluation Questionnaire

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this survey on the RESCALE platform and its impact on cybersecurity in software and hardware supply chains. The goal of this survey is to assess the effectiveness, adoption, and benefits of RESCALE's technologies in improving security, risk assessment, and compliance within software and hardware supply chains.

Your responses will help evaluate key performance indicators (KPIs) related to trust, security assessment accuracy, vulnerability detection, preparedness levels, and economic impact. The insights gathered will contribute to refining and optimizing the RESCALE approach to better meet industry needs.

This survey should take approximately 10–15 minutes to complete. All responses will be kept confidential and used solely for research purposes.

We appreciate your valuable time and input!

1 Survey Participant Profile

* 1.1 Which best describes your current role in the company?

- Researcher/Academic
- Security Expert
- Software Developer
- IT Manager
- Policy Maker
- Other

* 1.3 What is your level of experience with cybersecurity?

- Expert (e.g., security architect, cybersecurity consultant, or similar roles with extensive expertise)
- Advanced experience (e.g., hands-on experience with security frameworks, penetration testing, incident response)
- Intermediate experience (e.g., familiar with security tools, threat detection, and risk management)
- Basic knowledge (e.g., understanding of basic security concepts and practices)

No experience

* 1.4 What is the size of your company?

- Small (1–50 employees)
- Medium (51–200 employees)
- Large (201–1000 employees)
- Very Large (1001+ employees)
- I'm not sure / Prefer not to say

* 1.5 In which country is your company based?

2 Security Assessment and Vulnerability Detection

* 2.1 How long does it currently take to detect vulnerabilities in your software or hardware supply chain?

iKPI-17

- Less than a day
- 1–3 days
- 4–7 days
- More than a week

* 2.2 Which methods or tools does your organization use for evidence-based assessments of security and privacy properties of software and hardware components?

iKPI-6

- Static Code Analysis
- Dynamic Analysis
- Formal Verification
- Risk Assessment Frameworks
- Security Audits and Penetration Testing
- Threat Modeling
- Integration of AI/ML Models for Security and Privacy Detection
- Manual Code Reviews and Security Reviews
- Other

* 2.4 By using RESCALE, to what extent do you believe the time required to detect vulnerabilities in your supply chain be improved?

iKPI-17

- No improvement
- Slight improvement (1–5%)
- Moderate improvement (6–10%)
- Significant improvement (11–20%)
- Very significant improvement (more than 20%)
- I cannot estimate

* 2.5 To what extent do you believe that using the RESCALE platform will improve your organization's self-assessed preparedness levels for cybersecurity threats and incidents?

iKPI-8

- No improvement expected
- Some minor improvements, but overall impact is limited.
- Noticeable improvements, but some gaps remain.
- Major improvements in cybersecurity preparedness.
- Fully enhances preparedness and significantly reduces risks.

* 2.6 To what extent do you believe RESCALE improves system resilience against cyberattacks?

KPI1.1

- No improvement
- Slight improvement
- Moderate improvement
- Significant improvement
- Very significant improvement
- I cannot estimate

* 2.7 Has RESCALE helped identify vulnerabilities that were previously unknown in your system?

KPI2.3

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable

* 2.8 Did using RESCALE improve your team's understanding of cybersecurity vulnerabilities?

iKPI25

- No improvement
- Slight improvement
- Moderate improvement
- Significant improvement
- Very significant improvement
- I cannot estimate

3 Compliance with Security Standards

* 3.1 What Security Standards and proven guidelines has your organization adopted?

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- I do not know / It does not concern
- ISO/IEC 15408-1:2022 (Evaluation criteria for IT security)
- ISO/IEC 27001:2013 (Information Security Management System)
- ISO/IEC 27002:2022 (Code of Practice for Information Security Controls)
- ISO/IEC 27005:2022 (Guidance on managing information security risks)
- ISO/IEC 27034 (Application Security)
- ISO/IEC 27035 (Information security incident management)
- NIS 2 Directive (EU Directive on Security of Network and Information Systems)
- NIST SP 800-30 (Guide for Conducting Risk Assessments)

- * 3.2 To what extent do you believe the RESCALE platform can assist your organization in adopting and aligning with cybersecurity standards, such as the NIS Directive, GDPR, and other security frameworks?

iKPI-4

- Not at all
- To a small extent
- To a moderate extent
- To a large extent
- Completely

4 Adoption and Acceptance of RESCALE Solution

- * 4.1 How well do you think the RESCALE platform provides informative resources for both security and non-security experts?

KPI4.4

- Very poorly
- Poorly
- Neutral
- Well
- Very well

- 4.2 What improvements would you suggest to make the information provided more accessible for both security and non-security experts?

KPI4.4

- * 4.3 In your opinion, how beneficial is the use of blockchain technology in managing TBOM for security of software supply chains?

iKPI-1, iKPI-16:

- Not beneficial at all
- Slightly beneficial
- Moderately beneficial
- Very beneficial
- Extremely beneficial

- * 4.4 To what extent can introduction of blockchain-assisted TBOM updates increase your trust in the security of software supply chain?

iKPI-1, iKPI-16

- Not at all
- Slightly increased trust
- Moderately increased trust
- Significantly increased trust
- Fully increased trust

4.5 What are the main factors that would encourage or discourage your organization from fully adopting blockchain-assisted TBOM management processes?

iKPI-1

* 4.6 To what extent do you agree with the following statement: The technologies proposed and piloted through the RESCALE project are effective and adaptable across different environments.

iKPI-27

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

* 4.7 By what percentage do you estimate that the adoption of RESCALE can lead to cost savings in your company?

iKPI-24

- Less than 5%
- 5-10%
- 10-15%
- 15-20%
- More than 20%
- I cannot estimate

* 4.8 How likely are you to adopt the RESCALE platform in your organization?

KPI4.2, iKPI-11

- Very unlikely
- Unlikely
- Neutral
- Likely
- Very likely

DRAFT VERSION

Contact

rescale-all@isi.gr

DRAFT VERSION

B SAVE-ME Example

```
{
  "$schema": "https://json.schemastore.org/sarif-2.1.0",
  "version": "2.1.0",
  "runs": [
    {
      "tool": {
        "driver": {
          "name": "Erlang Analyzer",
          "fullName": "Erlang Vulnerability Analyzer",
          "version": "1.0.0",
          "informationUri": "https://sample_site.com",
          "rules": [
            {
              "id": "vulnerability-detection",
              "name": "Vulnerability Detection",
              "fullDescription": {
                "text": "Detects vulnerabilities in Erlang functions"
              }
            }
          ]
        }
      },
      "results": [
        {
          "ruleId": "vulnerability-detection",
          "message": {
            "text": "No vulnerability detected with confidence 3.59. Confidence
              for potential vulnerability: -3.28."
          },
          "locations": [
            {
              "physicalLocation": {
                "artifactLocation": {
                  "uri": "file:///Users/Shared/Files From d.localized/Materijali
                    /_RESCALE/save-me/test_dir/sample_erlang_module_n.erl"
                },
                "region": {
                  "startLine": 19,
                  "endLine": 19
                }
              }
            }
          ],
          "properties": {
            "confidence": 3.586867332458496
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

```
"ruleId": "vulnerability-detection",
"message": {
  "text": "No vulnerability detected with confidence 3.59. Confidence
          for potential vulnerability: -3.30."
},
"locations": [
  {
    "physicalLocation": {
      "artifactLocation": {
        "uri": "file:///Users/Shared/Files From d.localized/Materijali
              /_RESCALE/save-me/test_dir/sample_erlang_module_n.erl"
      },
      "region": {
        "startLine": 26,
        "endLine": 26
      }
    }
  }
],
"properties": {
  "confidence": 3.591543436050415
}
]
}
]
```

C DSCG Example

```
{
  "bomFormat": "CycloneDX",
  "specVersion": "1.6",
  "serialNumber": "urn:uuid:267cdf51-3dee-4757-9ed5-a9ba005eaa4d",
  "version": 1,
  "metadata": {
    "timestamp": "2025-03-22T06:24:38.534788Z",
    "authors": [
      {
        "name": "Some Company/person that wants to generate a DSCG for
          their binary",
        "email": "some@company.com"
      }
    ],
    "tools": {
      "components": [
        {
          "type": "application",
          "name": "ReSCALE DSCG Generator",
          "version": "1.0.0",
          "description": "A ReSCALE certified tool to generate DSCGs",
          "purl": "pkg:hex/dscg-generator@1.0.0"
        }
      ]
    }
  },
  "declarations": {
    "targets": {
      "components": [
        {
          "bom-ref": "ref_component_grisp",
          "description": "GRiSP Erlang Runtime Library",
          "externalReferences": [
            {
              "type": "vcs",
              "url": "https://github.com/grisp/grisp"
            }
          ],
          "licenses": [
            {
              "license": {
                "id": "Apache-2.0"
              }
            }
          ],
          "name": "grisp",
          "purl": "pkg:hex/grisp@2.6.0",
          "type": "application",
          "version": "2.6.0"
        }
      ]
    }
  }
}
```

```
    }
  ]
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"claims": [
  {
    "bom-ref": "Claim: RAISE found 6 instances of 500 errors!",
    "evidence": [
      "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at /api/
        blog/posts/189",
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        blog/posts",
      "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at /api/
        blog/posts",
      "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at /api/
        blog/posts",
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      "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at /api/
        blog/posts/189",
      "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at /api/
        blog/posts/189"
    ]
  },
  {
    "bom-ref": "urn:uuid:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3164f9cd1093",
    "evidence": [
      "Evidence: Faulty endpoints"
    ]
  }
],
"evidence": [
```

```
{
  "bom-ref": "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at
    /api/blog/posts/189",
  "description": "Evidence gathered by RAISE for 500",
  "data": [
    {
      "name": "RAISE Gadget Output",
      "contents": {
        "attachment": {
          "contentType": "application/json",
          "encoding": "base64",
          "content": "
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            ..."
          }
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
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    "description": "Evidence gathered by RAISE for 500",
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        "name": "RAISE Gadget Output",
        "contents": {
          "attachment": {
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            "encoding": "base64",
            "content": "
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              ..."
            }
          }
        }
      ]
    },
    {
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        /api/blog/posts",
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      "data": [
        {
          "name": "RAISE Gadget Output",
          "contents": {
            "attachment": {
              "contentType": "application/json",
              "encoding": "base64",
              "content": "
                ewogICJyZXF1ZXN0IjogewogICAgIlJlcXVlc3REYXR
                ..."
            }
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  }
}
```

```
        ..."
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "bom-ref": "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at
    /api/blog/posts",
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  "data": [
    {
      "name": "RAISE Gadget Output",
      "contents": {
        "attachment": {
          "contentType": "application/json",
          "encoding": "base64",
          "content": "
            ewogICJyZXF1ZXN0IjogewogICAgIlJlcXVlc3REYXR
            ..."
        }
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
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    /api/blog/posts",
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          "encoding": "base64",
          "content": "
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            ..."
        }
      }
    }
  ]
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{
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    /api/blog/posts",
  "description": "Evidence gathered by RAISE for 500",
  "data": [
    {
      "name": "RAISE Gadget Output",
```

```
        "contents": {
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                "encoding": "base64",
                "content": "
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                    ..."
            }
        }
    ],
},
{
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                }
            }
        }
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            }
        }
    ]
},
{
```

```
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    "name": "RAISE Gadget Output",
    "contents": {
      "attachment": {
        "contentType": "application/json",
        "encoding": "base64",
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          ..."
        }
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
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    /api/blog/posts",
  "description": "Evidence gathered by RAISE for 500",
  "data": [
    {
      "name": "RAISE Gadget Output",
      "contents": {
        "attachment": {
          "contentType": "application/json",
          "encoding": "base64",
          "content": "
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            ..."
          }
        }
      ]
    },
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              "encoding": "base64",
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                ..."
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          }
        ]
      },
      {
```

```
    }
  }
}
],
{
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            "encoding": "base64",
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              ..."
            }
          }
        ]
      },
      {
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          /api/blog/posts/184",
        "description": "Evidence gathered by RAISE for 500",
        "data": [
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            "name": "RAISE Gadget Output",
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```

```
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            ..."
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      }
    ]
  },
  {
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    "data": [
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            "encoding": "base64",
            "content": "
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              ..."
            }
          }
        }
      ]
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    {
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          "contents": {
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              "encoding": "base64",
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                ..."
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          }
        }
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    {
```

```
"bom-ref": "Evidence: 500 - Internal Server Error encountered at
/api/blog/posts/189",
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        "encoding": "base64",
        "content": "
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          ..."
      }
    }
  }
],
{
  "bom-ref": "urn:uuid:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3164f9cd1093",
  "description": "Faulty endpoints",
  "data": [
    {
      "name": "RescTest_faults_Test.py",
      "contents": {
        "attachment": {
          "content": "
            IyEvdXNyL2Jpbi91bnYgcHl0aG9uCGppbXBvcnQgan..."
        }
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "vulnerabilities": [
    {
      "id": "test_0_with500",
      "description": "# (500) GET:/api/search/cwe",
      "detail": "# Found 1 potential fault of type-code 100"
    },
    {
      "id": "test_1_with500",
      "description": "# (500) GET:/api/search/capec",
      "detail": "# Found 1 potential fault of type-code 100"
    }
  ],
  "externalReferences": [
    {
      "comment": "RESCALE SSCG",
      "hashes": [
```

```
    {
      "alg": "SHA-1",
      "content": "eee3fa7f88a4a3496903865e15b8fbf8065c1bd3"
    }
  ],
  "type": "bom",
  "url": "urn:cdx:bc2d4166-497f-42d0-86fc-3164f9cd1093/1"
}
]
```

D TBOM file example

```
{
  "bomFormat": "CycloneDX",
  "specVersion": "1.5",
  "serialNumber": "urn:uuid:d96c6a6c-5710-49f9-9335-04c5c33f06fd",
  "version": 1,
  "metadata": {
    "component": {
      "bom-ref": "tbom1-metadata",
      "name": "tbom1/metadata",
      "type": "file"
    },
    "supplier": {
      "name": "rescale-project.eu"
    },
    "timestamp": "2025-03-28T15:20:04.001499+00:00",
    "tools": {
      "components": [
        {
          "name": "TBOM Generator",
          "type": "application"
        },
        {
          "description": "Python library for CycloneDX",
          "externalReferences": [
            {
              "type": "build-system",
              "url": "https://github.com/CycloneDX/cyclonedx-python-lib/actions"
            },
            {
              "type": "distribution",
              "url": "https://pypi.org/project/cyclonedx-python-lib/"
            },
            {
              "type": "documentation",
              "url": "https://cyclonedx-python-library.readthedocs.io/"
            },
            {
              "type": "issue-tracker",
              "url": "https://github.com/CycloneDX/cyclonedx-python-lib/issues"
            },
            {
              "type": "license",
              "url": "https://github.com/CycloneDX/cyclonedx-python-lib/blob/main/LICENSE"
            },
            {
              "type": "release-notes",
              "url": "https://github.com/CycloneDX/cyclonedx-python-lib/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md"
            }
          ]
        }
      ]
    }
  }
}
```

```
    },
    {
      "type": "vcs",
      "url": "https://github.com/CycloneDX/cyclonedx-python-lib"
    },
    {
      "type": "website",
      "url": "https://github.com/CycloneDX/cyclonedx-python-lib/#readme"
    }
  ],
  "group": "CycloneDX",
  "licenses": [
    {
      "license": {
        "id": "Apache-2.0"
      }
    }
  ],
  "name": "cyclonedx-python-lib",
  "type": "library",
  "version": "9.1.0"
}
]
}
},
"components": [
  {
    "bom-ref": "bov-ref",
    "description": "a link to continuously-updated Bill of Vulnerabilities of : grisp",
    "externalReferences": [
      {
        "comment": "Link to BOV",
        "type": "distribution",
        "url": "https://sm.dev.rescale-project.eu/bovGet/urn:uuid:2c25b307-fb70-486f-9a8e-3eee4c3ec046"
      }
    ],
    "name": "BOV",
    "purl": "pkg:hex/grisp@2.6.0",
    "type": "file"
  },
  {
    "bom-ref": "dscg-ref",
    "description": "a link to the DSCG of: grisp",
    "externalReferences": [
      {
        "comment": "DSCG URL",
        "type": "distribution",
        "url": "https://sm.dev.rescale-project.eu/dscgGet/urn:uuid:3e671687-391b-41f5-a30f-a58921a69b78"
      }
    ]
  }
]
```

```
    }
  ],
  "name": "DSCG",
  "purl": "pkg:hex/a-very-nice-binary@1.0.0",
  "type": "file"
},
{
  "bom-ref": "sbom-ref",
  "description": "a link to the SBOM of: grisp",
  "externalReferences": [
    {
      "comment": "SBOM URL",
      "type": "distribution",
      "url": "https://sm.dev.rescale-project.eu/sbomGet/urn:uuid:7b0ba9e7-
        d293-4d05-a923-9527728610b9"
    }
  ],
  "name": "SBOM",
  "purl": "pkg:hex/grisp@2.6.0",
  "type": "file",
  "version": "1"
},
{
  "bom-ref": "sscg-ref",
  "description": "a link to the SSCG of: grisp",
  "externalReferences": [
    {
      "comment": "SSCG URL",
      "type": "distribution",
      "url": "https://sm.dev.rescale-project.eu/sscgGet/urn:uuid:bc2d4166
        -497f-42d0-86fc-3134f9cd1073"
    }
  ],
  "name": "SSCG",
  "purl": "pkg:hex/grisp@2.6.0",
  "type": "file"
}
],
"services": null,
"externalReferences": null,
"dependencies": [
  {
    "ref": "bov-ref"
  },
  {
    "ref": "dscg-ref"
  },
  {
    "ref": "sbom-ref"
  }
],
{
```

```
    "ref": "sscg-ref"  
  },  
  {  
    "dependsOn": [  
      "bov-ref",  
      "dscg-ref",  
      "sbom-ref",  
      "sscg-ref"  
    ],  
    "ref": "tbom1-metadata"  
  }  
]  
}
```

E SASTER-cli Example

```
{
  "$schema": "https://json.schemastore.org/sarif-2.1.0.json",
  "version": "2.1.0",
  "runs": [
    {
      "tool": {
        "driver": {
          "name": "Bandit",
          "organization": "PyCQA",
          "rules": [
            {
              "id": "B404",
              "name": "blacklist",
              "properties": {
                "tags": [
                  "security",
                  "external/cwe/cwe-78"
                ],
                "precision": "high"
              },
              "helpUri": "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/blacklists/blacklist_imports.html#b404-import-subprocess"
            },
            {
              "id": "B602",
              "name": "subprocess_popen_with_shell_equals_true",
              "properties": {
                "tags": [
                  "security",
                  "external/cwe/cwe-78"
                ],
                "precision": "high"
              },
              "helpUri": "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/b602_subprocess_popen_with_shell_equals_true.html"
            },
            {
              "id": "B608",
              "name": "hardcoded_sql_expressions",
              "properties": {
                "tags": [
                  "security",
                  "external/cwe/cwe-89"
                ],
                "precision": "low"
              },
              "helpUri": "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/b608_hardcoded_sql_expressions.html"
            }
          ]
        }
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

```
{
  "id": "B201",
  "name": "flask_debug_true",
  "properties": {
    "tags": [
      "security",
      "external/cwe/cwe-94"
    ],
    "precision": "medium"
  },
  "helpUri": "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/
    b201_flask_debug_true.html"
},
{
  "id": "B403",
  "name": "blacklist",
  "properties": {
    "tags": [
      "security",
      "external/cwe/cwe-502"
    ],
    "precision": "high"
  },
  "helpUri": "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/blacklists/
    blacklist_imports.html#b403-import-pickle"
},
{
  "id": "B324",
  "name": "hashlib",
  "properties": {
    "tags": [
      "security",
      "external/cwe/cwe-327"
    ],
    "precision": "high"
  },
  "helpUri": "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/
    b324_hashlib.html"
},
{
  "id": "B105",
  "name": "hardcoded_password_string",
  "properties": {
    "tags": [
      "security",
      "external/cwe/cwe-259"
    ],
    "precision": "medium"
  },
  "helpUri": "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/
    b105_hardcoded_password_string.html"
```

```
    },
    {
      "id": "B301",
      "name": "blacklist",
      "properties": {
        "tags": [
          "security",
          "external/cwe/cwe-502"
        ],
        "precision": "high"
      },
      "helpUri": "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/blacklists/blacklist_calls.html#b301-pickle"
    },
    {
      "id": "B113",
      "name": "request_without_timeout",
      "properties": {
        "tags": [
          "security",
          "external/cwe/cwe-400"
        ],
        "precision": "low"
      },
      "helpUri": "https://bandit.readthedocs.io/en/1.7.10/plugins/b113_request_without_timeout.html"
    }
  ],
  "version": "1.7.10",
  "semanticVersion": "1.7.10"
}
},
"invocations": [
  {
    "executionSuccessful": true,
    "endTimeUtc": "2024-10-01T08:35:40Z",
    "toolConfigurationNotifications": [
      {
        "message": {
          "text": "syntax error while parsing AST from file"
        },
        "level": "error",
        "locations": [
          {
            "physicalLocation": {
              "artifactLocation": {
                "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_1.py"
              }
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
]
```

```
    ]
  }
]
},
"properties": {
  "metrics": {
    "_totals": {
      "loc": 139,
      "nosec": 0,
      "skipped_tests": 0,
      "SEVERITY.UNDEFINED": 0,
      "CONFIDENCE.UNDEFINED": 0,
      "SEVERITY.LOW": 4,
      "CONFIDENCE.LOW": 2,
      "SEVERITY.MEDIUM": 3,
      "CONFIDENCE.MEDIUM": 2,
      "SEVERITY.HIGH": 4,
      "CONFIDENCE.HIGH": 7
    },
    "/data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_1.py": {
      "loc": 56,
      "nosec": 0,
      "skipped_tests": 0
    },
    "/data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_2.py": {
      "loc": 14,
      "nosec": 0,
      "skipped_tests": 0,
      "SEVERITY.UNDEFINED": 0,
      "SEVERITY.LOW": 1,
      "SEVERITY.MEDIUM": 0,
      "SEVERITY.HIGH": 1,
      "CONFIDENCE.UNDEFINED": 0,
      "CONFIDENCE.LOW": 0,
      "CONFIDENCE.MEDIUM": 0,
      "CONFIDENCE.HIGH": 2
    },
    "/data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_3.py": {
      "loc": 28,
      "nosec": 0,
      "skipped_tests": 0,
      "SEVERITY.UNDEFINED": 0,
      "SEVERITY.LOW": 0,
      "SEVERITY.MEDIUM": 1,
      "SEVERITY.HIGH": 1,
      "CONFIDENCE.UNDEFINED": 0,
      "CONFIDENCE.LOW": 1,
      "CONFIDENCE.MEDIUM": 1,
      "CONFIDENCE.HIGH": 0
    }
  },
}
```

```
"/data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_4.py": {
  "loc": 22,
  "nosec": 0,
  "skipped_tests": 0,
  "SEVERITY.UNDEFINED": 0,
  "SEVERITY.LOW": 3,
  "SEVERITY.MEDIUM": 1,
  "SEVERITY.HIGH": 2,
  "CONFIDENCE.UNDEFINED": 0,
  "CONFIDENCE.LOW": 0,
  "CONFIDENCE.MEDIUM": 1,
  "CONFIDENCE.HIGH": 5
},
"/data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/python_example_5.py": {
  "loc": 19,
  "nosec": 0,
  "skipped_tests": 0,
  "SEVERITY.UNDEFINED": 0,
  "SEVERITY.LOW": 0,
  "SEVERITY.MEDIUM": 1,
  "SEVERITY.HIGH": 0,
  "CONFIDENCE.UNDEFINED": 0,
  "CONFIDENCE.LOW": 1,
  "CONFIDENCE.MEDIUM": 0,
  "CONFIDENCE.HIGH": 0
}
},
"results": [
  {
    "message": {
      "text": "Consider possible security implications associated with
the subprocess module."
    },
    "level": "note",
    "locations": [
      {
        "physicalLocation": {
          "region": {
            "snippet": {
              "text": "import subprocess\n"
            },
            "endColumn": 18,
            "endLine": 1,
            "startColumn": 1,
            "startLine": 1
          },
          "artifactLocation": {
            "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
python_example_2.py"
          }
        },

```

```
        "contextRegion": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "import subprocess\n\ndef list_files(directory):\n"
          },
          "endLine": 3,
          "startLine": 1
        }
      }
    ],
    "properties": {
      "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
      "issue_severity": "LOW"
    },
    "ruleId": "B404",
    "ruleIndex": 0
  },
  {
    "message": {
      "text": "subprocess call with shell=True identified, security issue
      ."
    },
    "level": "error",
    "locations": [
      {
        "physicalLocation": {
          "region": {
            "snippet": {
              "text": " result = subprocess.check_output(command, shell=
              True)\n"
            },
            "endColumn": 62,
            "endLine": 8,
            "startColumn": 18,
            "startLine": 8
          },
          "artifactLocation": {
            "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
            python_example_2.py"
          },
          "contextRegion": {
            "snippet": {
              "text": " command = \"ls {}\".format(directory)\n result =
              subprocess.check_output(command, shell=True)\n print(
              result.decode())\n"
            },
            "endLine": 9,
            "startLine": 7
          }
        }
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

```

    ],
    "properties": {
      "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
      "issue_severity": "HIGH"
    },
    "ruleId": "B602",
    "ruleIndex": 1
  },
  {
    "message": {
      "text": "Possible SQL injection vector through string-based query
        construction."
    },
    "locations": [
      {
        "physicalLocation": {
          "region": {
            "snippet": {
              "text": " query = f\"SELECT * FROM users WHERE username = '{
                username}'\"\\n"
            },
            "endColumn": 65,
            "endLine": 24,
            "startColumn": 13,
            "startLine": 24
          },
          "artifactLocation": {
            "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
              python_example_3.py"
          },
          "contextRegion": {
            "snippet": {
              "text": " username = request.args.get('username')\\n query =
                f\"SELECT * FROM users WHERE username = '{username}'\"\\n
                \\n"
            },
            "endLine": 25,
            "startLine": 23
          }
        }
      }
    ],
    "properties": {
      "issue_confidence": "LOW",
      "issue_severity": "MEDIUM"
    },
    "ruleId": "B608",
    "ruleIndex": 2
  },
  {
    "message": {

```

```
    "text": "A Flask app appears to be run with debug=True, which
      exposes the Werkzeug debugger and allows the execution of
      arbitrary code."
  },
  "level": "error",
  "locations": [
    {
      "physicalLocation": {
        "region": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": " app.run(debug=True)\n"
          },
          "endColumn": 24,
          "endLine": 36,
          "startColumn": 5,
          "startLine": 36
        },
        "artifactLocation": {
          "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
            python_example_3.py"
        },
        "contextRegion": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": " init_db()\n app.run(debug=True)\n"
          },
          "endLine": 36,
          "startLine": 35
        }
      }
    }
  ],
  "properties": {
    "issue_confidence": "MEDIUM",
    "issue_severity": "HIGH"
  },
  "ruleId": "B201",
  "ruleIndex": 3
},
{
  "message": {
    "text": "Consider possible security implications associated with
      the subprocess module."
  },
  "level": "note",
  "locations": [
    {
      "physicalLocation": {
        "region": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "import subprocess\n"
          },
          "endColumn": 24,
          "endLine": 36,
          "startColumn": 5,
          "startLine": 36
        },
        "artifactLocation": {
          "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
            python_example_3.py"
        },
        "contextRegion": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "init_db()\n app.run(debug=True)\n"
          },
          "endLine": 36,
          "startLine": 35
        }
      }
    }
  ],
  "properties": {
    "issue_confidence": "MEDIUM",
    "issue_severity": "HIGH"
  },
  "ruleId": "B201",
  "ruleIndex": 3
}
```

```
        "endColumn": 18,
        "endLine": 1,
        "startColumn": 1,
        "startLine": 1
    },
    "artifactLocation": {
        "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
            python_example_4.py"
    },
    "contextRegion": {
        "snippet": {
            "text": "import subprocess\nimport os\nimport hashlib\n"
        },
        "endLine": 3,
        "startLine": 1
    }
}
],
"properties": {
    "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
    "issue_severity": "LOW"
},
"ruleId": "B404",
"ruleIndex": 0
},
{
    "message": {
        "text": "Consider possible security implications associated with
            pickle module."
    },
    "level": "note",
    "locations": [
        {
            "physicalLocation": {
                "region": {
                    "snippet": {
                        "text": "import pickle\n"
                    },
                    "endColumn": 14,
                    "endLine": 4,
                    "startColumn": 1,
                    "startLine": 4
                },
                "artifactLocation": {
                    "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
                        python_example_4.py"
                },
                "contextRegion": {
                    "snippet": {
                        "text": "import hashlib\nimport pickle\n\n"
```

```
    },
    "endLine": 5,
    "startLine": 3
  }
}
],
"properties": {
  "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
  "issue_severity": "LOW"
},
"ruleId": "B403",
"ruleIndex": 4
},
{
  "message": {
    "text": "subprocess call with shell=True identified, security issue
."
  },
  "level": "error",
  "locations": [
    {
      "physicalLocation": {
        "region": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": " subprocess.call(user_input, shell=True)\n"
          },
          "endColumn": 44,
          "endLine": 8,
          "startColumn": 5,
          "startLine": 8
        },
        "artifactLocation": {
          "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
python_example_4.py"
        },
        "contextRegion": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "def dangerous_function(user_input):\n subprocess.
call(user_input, shell=True)\n\n"
          },
          "endLine": 9,
          "startLine": 7
        }
      }
    }
  ],
  "properties": {
    "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
    "issue_severity": "HIGH"
  },
}
```

```
"ruleId": "B602",
"ruleIndex": 1
},
{
  "message": {
    "text": "Use of weak MD5 hash for security. Consider
            usedforsecurity=False"
  },
  "level": "error",
  "locations": [
    {
      "physicalLocation": {
        "region": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": " return hashlib.md5(password.encode('utf-8')).
                    hexdigest()\n"
          },
          "endColumn": 49,
          "endLine": 12,
          "startColumn": 12,
          "startLine": 12
        },
        "artifactLocation": {
          "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
                python_example_4.py"
        },
        "contextRegion": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": "def weak_hash(password):\n return hashlib.md5(
                    password.encode('utf-8')).hexdigest()\n\n"
          },
          "endLine": 13,
          "startLine": 11
        }
      }
    }
  ],
  "properties": {
    "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
    "issue_severity": "HIGH"
  },
  "ruleId": "B324",
  "ruleIndex": 5
},
{
  "message": {
    "text": "Possible hardcoded password: 'my_secret_key'"
  },
  "level": "note",
  "locations": [
    {
```

```

    "physicalLocation": {
      "region": {
        "snippet": {
          "text": "SECRET_KEY = \"my_secret_key\"\n"
        },
        "endColumn": 29,
        "endLine": 15,
        "startColumn": 14,
        "startLine": 15
      },
      "artifactLocation": {
        "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
          python_example_4.py"
      },
      "contextRegion": {
        "snippet": {
          "text": "# Vulnerability: Hardcoded secret key\nSECRET_KEY =
            \"my_secret_key\"\n\n"
        },
        "endLine": 16,
        "startLine": 14
      }
    }
  },
  "properties": {
    "issue_confidence": "MEDIUM",
    "issue_severity": "LOW"
  },
  "ruleId": "B105",
  "ruleIndex": 6
},
{
  "message": {
    "text": "Pickle and modules that wrap it can be unsafe when used to
      deserialize untrusted data, possible security issue."
  },
  "locations": [
    {
      "physicalLocation": {
        "region": {
          "snippet": {
            "text": " return pickle.loads(data)\n"
          },
          "endColumn": 30,
          "endLine": 19,
          "startColumn": 12,
          "startLine": 19
        },
        "artifactLocation": {

```

```
        "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
            python_example_4.py"
    },
    "contextRegion": {
        "snippet": {
            "text": "def insecure_deserialization(data):\n return pickle
                .loads(data)\n\n"
        },
        "endLine": 20,
        "startLine": 18
    }
}
],
"properties": {
    "issue_confidence": "HIGH",
    "issue_severity": "MEDIUM"
},
"ruleId": "B301",
"ruleIndex": 7
},
{
    "message": {
        "text": "Call to requests without timeout"
    },
    "locations": [
        {
            "physicalLocation": {
                "region": {
                    "snippet": {
                        "text": " response = requests.post(\"http://insecure-server.
                            com/api/data\", json=data)\n"
                    },
                    "endColumn": 79,
                    "endLine": 15,
                    "startColumn": 16,
                    "startLine": 15
                },
                "artifactLocation": {
                    "uri": "file:///data/uploads/user_1/project_1/files/
                        python_example_5.py"
                },
                "contextRegion": {
                    "snippet": {
                        "text": "def send_data(data):\n response = requests.post(\"
                            http://insecure-server.com/api/data\", json=data)\n
                            return response\n"
                    },
                    "endLine": 16,
                    "startLine": 14
                }
            }
        }
    ]
}
```

```
    }
  }
],
"properties": {
  "issue_confidence": "LOW",
  "issue_severity": "MEDIUM"
},
"ruleId": "B113",
"ruleIndex": 8
}
]
}
]
}
```

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